

Project Acronym	CAMEL
Project Title	CARDIOVASCULAR Risk Assessment via multimodal data analysis enabling personalised prevention strategies targeting MENOPAUSAL women
Project Number	101156210
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2024-STAYHLTH-01-05-two-stage
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA
Start date of the Project	December 2024
Duration of the Project	60 months

D14.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

(Version 2.0, 27/05/2025)

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Deliverable	D14.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
Work Package	WP14
Due Date	May 2025
Submission Date	28/05/2025
Lead Beneficiary	SIT
Version	2.0
Status	Submitted
Author name(s)	Giulia Onorati (SIT), Elisa Degasperi (SIT), Valentina Conotter (SIT), Bárbara Guerra (PARTICLE), Laura Patrícia (PARTICLE)
Contributor(s)	All partners
Reviewer(s)	(Anna Garcia-Elias) ASCIRES, (Rebeca García Betances) TREE
Approved by	28/05/2025
Keywords	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Stakeholders, Planning
Nature	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> DMP – Data Management Plan <input type="checkbox"/> DEM – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> DEC – Dissemination <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> SEN - Sensitive, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

The CAMEL Consortium consists of:

Participant	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Fundación Centro de Tecnologías de Interacción Visual y Comunicaciones Vicomtech	VICOM	Spain
2	A3Z advanced	A3Z	Spain
3	Keralty SAS	KER	Colombia
4	AE. Biokeralty Research Institute AIE	BK	Spain
5	Particle Summary	PARTICLE	Portugal
6	iBreve Limited	IBREVE	Ireland
7	Magdalena Clinic	MAG	Croatia
8	AE. Megi Health	MEGI	Croatia
9	Ethniko Kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athino	NKUA	Greece
10	Servicio Andaluz de Salud	SAS	Spain
11	AE. Fundación Pública Andaluza para la gestión de la investigación en salud de Sevilla	FISEVI	Spain
12	SocialIT Software e Consulting SRL	SIT	Italy
13	Trinity College Dublin	TCD	Ireland
14	Tree Technology SA	TREE	Spain
15	Viesoji Istaiga Vilniaus Universiteto Ligonine Santaros Klinikos	VULSK	Lithuania
16	Asociacion Centro de Investigacion Cooperativa en Biociencias	CIC	Spain
17	Exploraciones Radiológicas Especiales S.L. - ASCILRES	ASC	Spain
18	G Pace Ltd – Heart Rhythm Ireland	HRI	Ireland
19	Dublin City University	DCU	Ireland
20	Tampereen Korkeakoulusaatio SR – Tampere University	TAU	Finland
21	Ulma Medical Technologies S Coop	ULMA	Spain
22	Ben-Gurion University of The Negev	BGU	Israel
23	Smartnanosenose Innovation	SNSI	Israel
24	Asociación Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria Biogipuzkoa	BIO	Spain
25	Timelex	TLX	Belgium

Revision history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	08/04/2025	SIT	ToC
0.2	18/04/2025	SIT	First draft
0.3	02/05/2025	PARTICLE	Chapter 6, Exploitation strategy
0.4	09/05/2025	SIT	Second draft
0.5	13/05/2025	PARTICLE, VICOM	Third draft
1.0	15/05/2025	SIT	Final draft
1.1	23/05/2025	ASC	Document review
1.2	23/05/2025	TREE	Document review
2.0	27/05/2025	SIT	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive summary	8
1. Introduction.....	9
1.1 <i>Overview of the CAMEL project</i>	9
1.2 <i>Description of WP14 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.....</i>	9
1.3 <i>Purpose and scope of the deliverable</i>	10
1.4 <i>Structure of the deliverable</i>	10
1.5 <i>Relations with other WPs and tasks.....</i>	11
1.6 <i>Intended Audience.....</i>	11
2. Dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy.....	12
2.1 <i>Why to disseminate and communicate.....</i>	12
2.2 <i>To whom to disseminate and communicate</i>	14
2.2.1 <i>Healthcare professionals</i>	15
2.2.2 <i>Women aged 40-60.....</i>	15
2.2.3 <i>General public.....</i>	16
2.2.4 <i>Policy makers & health authorities.....</i>	16
2.2.5 <i>Research community.....</i>	17
2.2.6 <i>Technology and innovation sector</i>	17
2.2.7 <i>Community health organizations</i>	18
2.3 <i>What to disseminate and communicate.....</i>	18
2.4 <i>When to disseminate and communicate.....</i>	19
2.5 <i>How to disseminate and communicate.....</i>	20
2.6 <i>Communication mix matrix.....</i>	20
2.7 <i>Key messages tailored to target group.....</i>	22
2.8 <i>Dissemination obligations and rules.....</i>	30
2.9 <i>Internal coordination of dissemination activities</i>	31
3. Dissemination and communication tools and channels	32
3.1 <i>CAMEL visual identity</i>	32
3.1.1 <i>CAMEL logo</i>	32
3.1.2 <i>Templates</i>	34
3.1.3 <i>Presentation – Slide deck.....</i>	35
3.2 <i>Website.....</i>	36
3.3 <i>CAMEL branded materials</i>	38
3.3.1 <i>CAMEL brochure</i>	38
3.3.2 <i>Poster.....</i>	38
3.3.3 <i>Roll-up.....</i>	39
3.3.4 <i>Videos</i>	40
3.4 <i>Press releases</i>	40
3.5 <i>Newsletters.....</i>	41
3.6 <i>Social media channels</i>	41

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

3.7	<i>Partners communication tools and channels</i>	44
3.8	<i>CARAMEL CVD Prevention Portal</i>	44
3.9	<i>Publications</i>	45
3.10	<i>Networking and clustering activities</i>	46
3.10.1	<i>Synergies with related projects</i>	47
3.10.2	<i>Networks</i>	48
3.10.3	<i>Stakeholder community</i>	48
3.10.4	<i>External and partner-led events</i>	49
3.10.5	<i>Events organized by the CARAMEL consortium</i>	49
3.11	<i>CARAMEL External Advisory Board</i>	49
3.12	<i>Women engagement strategies</i>	50
4.	Monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities	50
4.1	<i>Communication and dissemination KPIs</i>	50
4.2	<i>Communication and dissemination monitoring</i>	51
5.	Guide on dissemination and communication activities	53
6.	Exploitation strategy	54
6.1	<i>Key exploitable results</i>	55
6.2	<i>Market analysis</i>	56
6.3	<i>Intellectual property rights audit</i>	57
6.4	<i>CARAMEL Business Plan</i>	58
7.	Conclusions	58
Appendices	60
	<i>Appendix I – Related projects</i>	60
	<i>Appendix II – Established networks</i>	63
	<i>Appendix III - Known stakeholders</i>	64
	<i>Appendix IV – Relevant future events</i>	66
	<i>Appendix V – Events organized by partners</i>	68

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 CAMEL LOGO, VERTICAL AND HORIZONTAL.....	33
FIGURE 2 CAMEL MODULAR ELEMENTS.....	33
FIGURE 3 CAMEL PRESENTATIONS TEMPLATE	34
FIGURE 4 CAMEL LETTERHEAD	35
FIGURE 5 CAMEL DOCUMENTS TEMPLATE	35
FIGURE 6 SLIDES FROM THE CAMEL PROJECT PRESENTATION	36
FIGURE 7 CAMEL PROJECT WEBSITE HOMEPAGE.....	37
FIGURE 8 CAMEL BROCHURE	38
FIGURE 9 CAMEL POSTER.....	39
FIGURE 10 CAMEL ROLL-UP	39
FIGURE 11 STILLS FROM CAMEL VIDEO	40
FIGURE 12 CAMEL LINKEDIN ACCOUNT.....	42
FIGURE 13 CAMEL FACEBOOK ACCOUNT	43
FIGURE 14 CAMEL YOUTUBE ACCOUNT	43

List of Tables

TABLE 1 ALIGNMENT BETWEEN CAMEL SOS AND CDE STRATEGY	14
TABLE 2 COMMUNICATION MIX MATRIX	21
TABLE 3 CAMEL CDE RULES AND OBLIGATIONS.....	31
TABLE 5 CAMEL PRELIMINARY KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	55

Abbreviation

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BP	Blood Pressure
CDE	Communication, dissemination and Exploitation
CV	Cardiovascular
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
CVD-RA	Cardiovascular Disease Risk Assessment
DY	Dyslipidaemia
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission
HT	Hypertension
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KER	Key Explotable Result
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KSF	Key Success Factors
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
NMR	Nuclear magnetic spectroscopy
RA	Risk Assessment
RFs	Risk Factors
RWD	Real-World Data
SO	Specific Objective
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document describes the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan for the Horizon Europe project CAMEL, which develops AI-powered, gender-sensitive tools for cardiovascular disease prevention in women aged 40–60.

The CDE strategy defines how the project will raise awareness towards target groups, engage stakeholders, promote the uptake of results, and ensure long-term impact across scientific, clinical, policy, and community sectors. The strategy is structured around five guiding questions (why, to whom, what, when, and how), and it aligns outreach actions with the needs and expectations of key target groups, including healthcare professionals, women aged 40–60, general public, policymakers and healthcare authorities, research communities, technology and innovation sector, and community health organisations. It also provides a detailed overview of the communication tools and channels, ranging from digital platforms and scientific publications to social media campaigns and stakeholder events, used to ensure broad engagement and targeted dissemination.

The plan aims to maximise CAMEL's visibility and reach, foster adoption of its innovations, and support the broader mission of improving cardiovascular health for women through inclusive, evidence-based digital solutions. Designed as a living document, the CDE Plan will evolve alongside the project, to reflect project progress and activities, stakeholder feedback, and emerging dissemination and exploitation opportunities.

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview of the CARMEL project

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of death among women in Europe, with an especially sharp increase in risk during and after menopause. Despite these realities, CVD remains underdiagnosed and undertreated in women, as current risk prediction models often fail to account for sex- and gender-specific factors, and these continue to be underrepresented in prevention strategies and healthcare policies.

The Horizon Europe project CARMEL responds to this urgent public health challenge by developing AI-powered tools for personalised risk assessment and prevention strategies tailored to women aged 40–60. At the core of CARMEL's approach is the integration of multiple data sources, such as clinical records, medical imaging, wearable devices, and lifestyle information, to develop AI-based models capable of assessing risk levels and tailoring prevention plans.

By leveraging emerging technologies, CARMEL will enable women to take proactive steps toward their heart health through self-assessment tools and a modular digital ecosystem designed for empowerment and personalised self-management. In addition, the project will incorporate advanced diagnostic tools and new biomarkers, including non-invasive skin nanosensors and Nuclear Magnetic Spectroscopy-based (NMR) lipoprotein and inflammation markers, to enable earlier and more accurate risk assessment.

With the involvement of 25 partners across 11 countries, CARMEL aims to bridge gaps in research, care, and policy by delivering scalable solutions that address the specific needs of women during peri- and menopause, with particular attention to inclusiveness, including women with intellectual disabilities.

1.2 Description of WP14 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Work Package 14 (WP14) CDE plays a pivotal role in both promoting CARMEL's innovative approach to the personalised prevention of CVD and ensuring that its results achieve lasting impact and uptake. Coordinated by Social IT (SIT), WP14 sets the foundations for outreach, stakeholder engagement, capacity-building, and strategic exploitation.

The **specific objectives** of WP14 are as follows:

- To define and implement a CDE Plan, to communicate about CARMEL's approach, objectives, progress, and achievements;
- To prepare awareness-raising and training materials and tools, empowering and engaging women in the understanding and self-management of their CVD-related health, and supporting their participation in project activities;
- To define an exploitation strategy for the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and establish the potential business models and exploitation pathways for the market uptake of the CARMEL results;
- To capitalise on alliances with sister projects and initiatives, ensuring broad dissemination and creating synergies at EU and international levels.

WP14 is structured into the following tasks:

- **T14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities (Lead: SIT)**
Development and implementation of the CDE Plan, targeting effective outreach and engagement with tailored content and tools including the website, press releases, social media, newsletter, and event participation;
- **T14.2 Awareness raising and training about women's CV health (Lead: DCU)**

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Creation of public health literacy materials and structured training resources for both women and healthcare professionals. These include fact sheets, video resources, guidance on clinical pathways, biomarkers, risk models, and preventive interventions. All training materials developed in this task will be accessible through the Women's CVD Prevention Portal;

- **T14.3 Women, clinicians and patients' engagement (Lead: TCD)**

Design and implementation of engagement strategies across all clinical and research activities, including co-creation processes and feedback loops that ensure inclusivity and real-world relevance;

- **T14.4 Networking and clustering activities (Lead: SIT)**

Development of strategic alliances with related initiatives, clustering with projects from the same or adjacent domains, and joint dissemination activities to maximise resource efficiency and sector impact.

WP15 and WP16 will build directly upon the foundations laid by WP14, continuing its communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in the second and third reporting periods, with a focus on assessing the feasibility, adoption and sustainability of CARMEL's tools and models for public health and healthcare integration.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The purpose of this document is twofold: first, to define a roadmap for all communication and dissemination activities carried out under WP14-15-16, including messages, tools, channels, audiences, and responsibilities; second, to establish the foundations for the exploitation of CARMEL's KER, aligning scientific, technological, and societal value creation with long-term sustainability goals.

The CDE Plan will guide consortium partners in communicating with target groups and stakeholders through the tools and channels detailed in Chapter 3, such as the project website, press releases, event participation, social media presence, and newsletters. These tools will be used strategically to deliver tailored messages that resonate with the needs, expectations, and knowledge levels of each target group. This CDE Plan is intended to be a living document. It may be revised and updated during the course of the project to reflect newly emerging needs, stakeholder inputs, or strategic opportunities. Such modifications will be reported in the three Periodic Reports to be submitted to the EC. Updates will be based on ongoing feedback, the performance of CDE actions, and lessons learned from engagement with target audiences. The implementation and impact of the activities defined in this plan will be revisited in later deliverables, notably in D14.4, D15.2, D16.3 and D16.4.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is organised into seven chapters, each addressing in detail the core components of the CDE strategy of the CARMEL project.

- **Chapter 1** introduces the CARMEL project and Work Package 14. It outlines the purpose and scope of this deliverable, its relevance within the project, and its connections with other work packages and tasks.
- **Chapter 2** presents the overall CDE strategy, structured around five guiding questions (why, to whom, what, when, how). It defines target audiences, key messages, a communication matrix, and internal coordination mechanisms.
- **Chapter 3** details the tools and channels adopted to implement the strategy, including the project website, visual identity, branded materials, media presence, and the Women's CVD Prevention Portal. It also describes dissemination activities led by individual partners and networking opportunities.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- **Chapter 4** outlines the monitoring and evaluation framework to assess the implementation, outreach, and impact of communication and dissemination activities. This includes a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- **Chapter 5** serves as a practical guide for project partners to ensure consistent, effective, and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant CDE actions throughout the project duration.
- **Chapter 6** describes the preliminary exploitation strategy, including the identification of KERs, early-stage market potential, and next steps planned to support exploitation sustainability and future adoption of results, to be implemented in WP15 and WP16.
- **Chapter 7** concludes the deliverable and provides an outlook on future updates to be reported in follow-up deliverables.
- **Annexes** provide complementary information on networks, events, stakeholders, and synergies with related initiatives.

1.5 Relations with other WPs and tasks

WP14 acts as a transversal enabler across the whole CAMEL project, ensuring that communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are closely aligned with all the objectives of the project. For this reason, WP14 supports cross-cutting collaboration with **all the other WPs** to ensure that the project's scientific, technological, and clinical outputs are translated into accessible, impactful communication and long-term exploitation strategies, amplifying the visibility and uptake of results emerging from all WPs.

In particular, during the initial phase of the project, T14.3 (women, clinicians and patients' engagement) is strongly interlinked with **WP4** (Women engagement and co-creation). Indeed, outputs from WP4, including the mapping of women's needs, expectations, and preferences, will provide essential input for shaping inclusive and representative dissemination messages and engagement formats. At the same time, the strategies developed in T14.3 support the effective visibility of WP4 co-creation activities, creating a bidirectional feedback loop between engagement and communication. A coordinated approach between WP4 and T14.3 ensures that stakeholder engagement is not only robust and inclusive but also integrated into the broader impact strategy of the project from the outset.

In addition, strong synergies exist between T14.2 and **T9.5** (Development of the CAMEL Self-Assessment App – asApp). The asApp will support women in the self-assessment of their CVD risk, will be accessible via Android app stores and will have a web interface connected to the Women's CVD Prevention Portal. Close collaboration between T14.2 and T9.5 will ensure that the app delivers intuitive, user-friendly, and evidence-based guidance, seamlessly aligned with the educational and empowerment objectives of the CAMEL project.

Furthermore, WP14 maintains a strong operational alignment with **WP11, WP12, and WP13**, which are responsible for the design, implementation, and monitoring of the clinical studies (observational and interventional) that will validate the CAMEL models and digital tools. Specifically, dissemination outputs from WP14 (and subsequently from WP15 and WP16) will support the visibility of these studies across the project's clinical sites, enhance recruitment efforts, and ensure transparent communication of studies' milestones, interim data, and preliminary findings.

1.6 Intended Audience

The intended audience of this deliverable are the CAMEL consortium partners, as it describes the strategy and tools related to the project's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. It is also intended for the EC services, since this document describes CAMEL communication, dissemination and exploitation Following the agreed Description of Action,

D14.1 is available for Public (PUB) access. The Deliverable will be disseminated once approved by the EC in CARMEL's project website and Zenodo community, a multi-disciplinary, open-access research repository.

2. Dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy

The purpose of this Chapter is to define the strategic approach that will guide all CDE activities throughout the CARMEL project. These activities aim to raise awareness and to ensure that the project's vision, scientific progress, and technological outputs are effectively shared, understood, and taken up by all relevant stakeholders. Moreover, the CDE strategy is also designed to support active engagement, foster co-creation, and prepare the ground for the uptake and long-term sustainability of its results. As such, it plays a central role in achieving CARMEL's mission to transform CVD prevention for menopausal women through an inclusive, AI-enabled, data-driven approach.

In line with the Horizon Europe expectations and the Grant Agreement, the strategy described in this Chapter is structured around a set of guiding questions that address the rationale, content, audiences, timing, and methods of CDE actions:

- **Why** disseminate, communicate and exploit?
- **What** kind of information and outputs should be shared?
- **To whom** are these actions addressed?
- **When** is the right moment to disseminate and communicate, in relation to the project's lifecycle?
- **How** will communication and dissemination be carried out?

The answers to these questions are detailed in the sub-sections below and serve as a strategic compass for all project partners. The practical implementation of this strategy, including tools, visual identity, materials, and communication channels, is presented in Chapter 3.

The dissemination and communication activities of the project will be taking place throughout the whole project duration (five years), to guarantee that all relevant stakeholders receive updates and news related to CARMEL.

All CARMEL project partners are actively involved in dissemination, communication and exploitation activities and are expected to contribute to their implementation throughout the project's duration.

2.1 Why to disseminate and communicate

CDE activities are essential to the successful implementation of the CARMEL project. They serve not only to raise awareness of the project and its innovations, but also to foster engagement, promote the uptake and sustainability of results, and ensure that CARMEL's impact extends beyond its duration and beyond the research community.

These CDE plan efforts are guided by a clear set of strategic goals, as outlined in the project proposal:

- **Raising awareness:** increasing public understanding of CVD disease prevention, with a focus on empowering women aged 40–60 to actively manage their CVD health through greater awareness of risks and early intervention strategies;
- **Establishing synergies and cooperation:** promoting structured collaboration between citizens, especially women, and public authorities in the health and education sectors, with the aim of strengthening collective efforts in the prevention and management of CVD;

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- **Sharing knowledge and good practices:** disseminating improved knowledge, best practices and experiential insights related to CVD risk communication, monitoring and management, with the aim of fostering more resilient communities and enhancing individuals' capacity for effective health self-management.
- **Disseminating results of risk assessment models and IT tools:** promoting awareness and understanding of the outputs generated by the project's digital solutions, to encourage their acceptance and use in personal health management;
- **Advocating policy recommendations:** delivering well-researched, actionable policy recommendations aimed at strengthening EU strategies on CVD prevention, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups such as women aged 40–60. This includes promoting citizen engagement in policy dialogues through participatory approaches, ensuring that women's voices contribute meaningfully to shaping public health policies.
- **Increasing adoption and integration:** fostering the uptake of CARMEL's risk models and tools by key user groups (e.g., healthcare professionals, policymakers and women aged 40-60), ensuring their incorporation into real-world health practices for personalised CVD prevention.

The CDE plan is an essential instrument for the successful implementation of CARMEL's specific objectives (SOs). Each communication, dissemination and exploitation action are designed to amplify the visibility, relevance, and uptake of project results. The table below is an overview of how the CDE strategy supports the achievement of each specific objective.

Specific Objective	CDE strategy
SO1: To develop novel data-driven models for risk stratification, personalised to menopausal women, integrating multimodal sources of information including biomedical, behavioural, social and environmental factors	Ensuring that the scientific rationale, methodological innovation and potential impact of the models are effectively communicated to the research, clinical, and digital health communities, enabling early visibility and stakeholder interest.
SO2: To establish a modular digital ecosystem (including a web portal and app ecosystem) to support women's self-assessment, awareness and personalised CVD prevention	Promoting awareness and understanding of the ecosystem among women and healthcare professionals, facilitating its usability, trust, and potential adoption.
SO3: To generate real-world evidence on the applicability and effectiveness of the models and the digital ecosystem via four clinical studies (1 retrospective, 3 prospective) across five countries	Supporting visibility and transparency of clinical studies, sharing milestones and preliminary insights, and enhancing recruitment and engagement with participants and local stakeholders.
SO4: To co-create the tools and strategies with women themselves (including those with intellectual disabilities) to ensure inclusiveness, accessibility and relevance	Supporting and amplifying engagement activities to ensure that women's experiences, needs and perspectives are represented and visible in public-facing communications.
SO5: To empower women aged 40–60, increase health literacy and promote the adoption of healthy behaviours for CVD prevention	Creating targeted awareness materials and gender-sensitive educational content to empower women aged 40–60, increase health literacy, and promote the adoption of healthy behaviours for CVD prevention.
SO6: To support clinical and public health innovation, by demonstrating the	Drafting and disseminating policy-oriented communication and dissemination to promote dialogue with healthcare authorities and

feasibility of integrating the models and tools in diverse healthcare systems	integration of CAMEL outputs into clinical guidelines and practices.
SO7: To ensure long-term sustainability and exploitation of project results, including market readiness and alignment with regulatory frameworks	Showcasing CAMEL results, engaging healthcare stakeholders, industry stakeholders and regulators, and preparing the ground for the continuation and scaling of the results beyond the project's duration.
SO8: To contribute to EU policies and global strategies on women's health and non-communicable diseases prevention through policy recommendations and stakeholder engagement	Designing and disseminating policy briefs, active participation in health policy forums, and engagement with European and international stakeholders to influence strategic agendas.

Table 1 Alignment between CAMEL SOs and CDE strategy

2.2 To whom to disseminate and communicate

The success of CAMEL's CDE strategy relies on a clear understanding of the diverse target audiences the project aims to reach, engage, and impact. These audiences reflect the multifaceted nature of CAMEL, which brings together research, healthcare, technology, and public engagement to promote a gender-sensitive, data-driven model of CVD prevention tailored to women aged 40-60.

In line with the project's objectives and stakeholder mapping outlined in the proposal, the CDE strategy distinguishes between different categories of stakeholders, each with specific informational needs, motivations, and roles in supporting CAMEL's implementation and long-term sustainability. Communication and dissemination activities are therefore designed to be tailored and audience-specific, ensuring that key messages are accessible, relevant, and actionable for each group.

The primary target groups (TGs) identified for the CAMEL project are as follows:

- **Healthcare professionals (HCPs)**, including clinicians, nurses, and general practitioners, are essential for integrating the project's findings and digital tools into preventive care;
- **Women aged 40–60**, including those with intellectual disabilities, represent the project's core end-users and primary beneficiaries;
- **General public**, whose awareness and understanding of gender-specific CVD prevention can amplify societal impact;
- **Policy makers and health authorities**, whose support is key to the adoption and sustainability of CAMEL's models and recommendations at institutional and systemic levels;
- **Research community**, including experts in AI tools, digital health interventions and screening technologies, with whom knowledge-sharing is essential to maximise scientific relevance and replication;
- **Technology and innovation sector**, particularly developers, digital health companies, and industry stakeholders with a role in scaling, commercialising, or integrating CAMEL's exploitable results;
- **Community health organisations**, can support outreach of CAMEL's tool, amplify messages, and foster inclusive engagement with underserved or vulnerable populations.

Each of these groups will be addressed through dedicated dissemination and communication actions, with specific channels, formats, and engagement mechanisms tailored to their profiles and expected involvement in the project.

The next sections provide a more detailed description of each TG, outlining their relevance to the project, the rationale for targeting them, and the adopted approach to engage them effectively.

2.2.1 Healthcare professionals

Healthcare professionals (HCPs) represent a key stakeholder group for the dissemination and communication efforts of CARAMEL. Their role is crucial in translating the project's scientific advancements and digital innovations into meaningful preventive practices in real-world clinical settings. The engagement of HCPs is also vital to ensure that the project's outcomes are aligned with the needs and workflows of frontline health services.

CARAMEL targets a wide spectrum of HCPs, including general practitioners, cardiologists, gynaecologists, nurses, and any public health professionals who are directly or indirectly involved in women's health and CVD risk management. Given their dual function as both recipients and transmitters of health knowledge, these professionals are strategically positioned to foster trust, encourage adoption of the project's tools, and support the empowerment of women in managing their CVD related health.

Within the CARAMEL ecosystem, HCPs are expected to:

- Act as early adopters and validators of the project's digital tools and risk stratification models;
- Facilitate the integration of personalised prevention into existing care pathways;
- Support women's empowerment through tailored counselling and preventive advice;
- Provide essential feedback for the refinement and clinical applicability of project outputs.

Their engagement is thus fundamental not only for enhancing the project's reach and credibility, but also for ensuring the clinical relevance, usability, and long-term sustainability of CARAMEL's results.

2.2.2 Women aged 40-60

Women aged 40–60 represent the primary TG of the CARAMEL project and the ultimate beneficiaries of its innovations. The transition through midlife and menopause is marked by physiological and hormonal transitions related to menopause that can increase vulnerability to CVD, and influence health trajectories. Despite this, women in this age group remain largely underrepresented in CVD research and underserved in preventive healthcare. They are highly relevant to the project as traditional CVD risk models often fail to account for gender-specific factors and the cumulative impact of behavioural, social, and biological determinants affecting women during this period.

Within the CARAMEL ecosystem, women aged 40–60 are not only recipients of information and services, but also active contributors and co-creators. Their engagement is essential to:

- Co-create/design CARAMEL's digital tools that are inclusive, relevant, and accessible;
- Provide insights into lived experiences, needs, expectations, and perceived barriers to CVD prevention;
- Validate the usability and acceptability of the CARAMEL digital ecosystem;
- Act as community-level multipliers by promoting awareness and behavioural change among peers.

By placing women at the centre of its dissemination and engagement strategy, CARAMEL seeks to promote a model of CVD prevention that is participatory, empowering, and

responsive to gendered health trajectories, thereby maximising both individual and societal impact.

2.2.3 General public

The general public represents an important secondary TG for the CARMEL project, particularly in terms of raising overall awareness about CVD as a gendered health issue and promoting a more inclusive understanding for women's CVD health needs. While not directly involved in the clinical or technological aspects of the project, the public plays a key role in shaping attitudes, behaviours, and societal support for preventive action.

The relevance of this group lies in its potential to influence the socio-cultural environment in which women aged 40–60 make health decisions. Increasing public awareness about the specific CVD risks faced by women, especially during and after the menopausal transition, helps to combat gender bias in health narratives and promotes a more supportive ecosystem for individual and collective prevention efforts.

Within the CARMEL ecosystem, the general public is expected to:

- Benefit from improved health literacy and broader access to information on gender-specific CVD risk factors;
- Contribute to social change by challenging stereotypes and misconceptions around CVD as a “male disease”;
- Act as informal support networks for women in their families, communities, and workplaces;

By targeting the general public with accessible, engaging, and evidence-based content, CARMEL aims to foster a culture of shared responsibility in CVD prevention, amplifying the societal impact of the project beyond the immediate circle of clinical stakeholders and end-users.

2.2.4 Policy makers & health authorities

Policy makers and health authorities are a strategic TG for CARMEL, given their central role in shaping public health priorities, funding frameworks, regulatory environments, and the integration of innovative approaches into healthcare systems. Their support is essential to ensure that the project's outcomes translate into long-term, system-wide change.

Their engagement enables CARMEL to align its tools, models, and recommendations with institutional frameworks, national and regional health strategies, and broader EU policy agendas on gender equity and non-communicable disease (NCD) prevention.

Within the CARMEL ecosystem, policy makers and health authorities are expected to:

- Assess the policy relevance and scalability of CARMEL's gender-sensitive risk models, digital tools, and engagement strategies;
- Integrate evidence generated by the project into guidelines, programmes, and funding schemes;
- Support the institutional uptake of CARMEL results at regional, national, and EU levels;
- Foster policy dialogues, cross-sector collaboration, and innovation in health systems to amplify the impact of CARMEL's results.

By engaging with these actors through targeted dissemination and policy-oriented communication, CARMEL aims to contribute to a more enabling policy environment for gender-sensitive CVD prevention and to promote the long-term sustainability and integration of its results within public health systems.

2.2.5 Research community

The research community is a key dissemination audience for CAMEL, encompassing experts and institutions across biomedical, clinical, behavioural, social, environmental, and digital health sciences. This group plays a central role in validating the scientific quality of the project's work, ensuring knowledge transfer, and enabling replication, scaling, and further development of its methodologies and findings.

This audience is highly relevant to the project as it contributes to the consolidation of an evidence-based foundation for gender-specific CVD prevention. Engaging with researchers ensures that the innovative approaches developed in CAMEL are critically assessed, contextualised, and extended through interdisciplinary collaboration.

Within the CAMEL ecosystem, the research community is expected to:

- Engage with, build upon, and extend the project's scientific outputs, including models, datasets, and methodologies;
- Participate in knowledge exchange through international conferences and interdisciplinary research networks;
- Contribute to the visibility, credibility, and peer recognition of CAMEL's results;
- Support the integration of CAMEL's innovations in research agenda and future interdisciplinary research initiatives.

By targeting the research community through high-quality scientific communication and open knowledge sharing (e.g., via Zenodo), CAMEL aims to advance interdisciplinary collaboration, reinforce its contribution to the European Research Area, and embed its innovations within future research and education frameworks.

2.2.6 Technology and innovation sector

The technology and innovation sector represents a critical stakeholder group for the dissemination and exploitation of CAMEL's digital outputs. This audience includes developers, digital health companies, SMEs, med-tech innovators, start-ups, and industry stakeholders with the capacity to further develop, integrate, commercialise, or scale up the project's tools and services.

Their relevance to the project lies in their ability to bridge the gap between research and market, translating technological prototypes into viable solutions that can reach end-users through sustainable models. In particular, this group plays a key role in supporting the exploitation pathways for specific CAMEL's KERs, such as the AI-based risk stratification models and the digital Apps ecosystem.

Within the CAMEL ecosystem, the technology and innovation sector are expected to:

- Validate the technological feasibility, commercial viability, and market potential of project results;
- Collaborate in the development of business models and go-to-market strategies;
- Generate business opportunities for the integration of CAMEL results with existing digital health platforms or service frameworks;
- Contribute to the long-term sustainability of CAMEL results through investment, partnerships, licensing agreements or productization.

Through targeted exploitation-oriented engagement with this sector, CAMEL aims to strengthen its innovation dimension, promote technology transfer, and lay the foundations for real-world impact and scalability beyond the project's duration.

2.2.7 Community health organizations

Community health organizations, including NGOs, advocacy groups, women's associations, patient networks, and local health promoters, are valuable intermediaries in CARMEL's dissemination and engagement strategy. These actors often work directly with the populations targeted by the project and play a central role in supporting awareness, access, and equity in health promotion.

They are particularly relevant to CARMEL due to their trusted relationships with other key TGs, including women aged 40–60, healthcare professionals, and vulnerable communities, as well as their experience in delivering inclusive and culturally sensitive health initiatives. Their involvement helps ensure that CARMEL's messages and tools are adapted to local needs, effectively disseminated within communities, and reinforced through culturally sensitive engagement and behaviour change initiatives.

Within the CARMEL ecosystem, community health organizations are expected to:

- Act as amplifiers of CARMEL's messages and tools at local and regional levels;
- Facilitate the uptake of CARMEL's tools;
- Support co-creation and feedback loops by connecting the project with community-based experiences;
- Promote behavioural change and advocacy through community-based education and peer support initiatives.

By engaging with these organizations, CARMEL seeks to embed its work within existing networks of trust and care, enhancing inclusiveness, reach, and real-world relevance.

2.3 What to disseminate and communicate

This Section outlines the key types of content that CARMEL will produce and share throughout the project's lifecycle. In alignment with the overall CDE strategy, dissemination efforts will be guided by the nature and relevance of these contents, ensuring that they are appropriately packaged and delivered to their intended audiences.

The list below provides a structured overview of the main thematic content areas that will serve as the basis for all communication and dissemination activities. These categories reflect both the expected outputs of the project and the diverse dimensions of its innovation and impact.

- **Scientific and technical outputs:** including AI-based risk models, digital ecosystem components, datasets, algorithms and validation reports;
- **Clinical results:** findings and insights from the retrospective and prospective clinical studies conducted in six sites;
- **Participatory and co-design findings:** insights from workshops, surveys, and interviews involving over 6,000 women, including those with intellectual disabilities;
- **Health education materials:** infographics, guides, explainer videos and brochures to promote heart health and risk awareness;
- **Policy and strategic outputs:** policy briefs, recommendations and white papers to support public health integration and policy uptake;
- **Cross-project synergies:** outputs from clustering activities, EU-level collaborations and joint events with other Horizon-funded initiatives;
- **Training and capacity-building materials:** resources designed to support the adoption of CARMEL tools by healthcare providers, community actors, and local networks.
- **Ethical, legal and regulatory guidelines:** content addressing data protection, inclusiveness, and alignment with European health innovation standards;
- **User experience and usability insights:** evidence collected through user testing and feedback loops to improve the relevance and accessibility of CARMEL solutions.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

A more detailed alignment of each content type with specific objectives, target audiences, tools and timing are provided in Section 2.6 (Communication Mix Matrix).

In addition to these thematic categories, the project will also disseminate **operational and narrative contents** to ensure transparency, engagement and community relevance. These include updates on project milestones and deliverables, meeting highlights, event participation, publication announcements, media coverage, and opportunities for stakeholder involvement. These items will be adapted to the tone, format and timing of each communication channel (e.g. newsletters, social media, website, policy briefs) to ensure consistency and resonance across the dissemination ecosystem.

2.4 When to disseminate and communicate

The timing of communication and dissemination activities in CAMEL is strategically aligned with the project's lifecycle and the progressive availability of results. A phased approach ensures that key messages and materials are delivered at the right moment, maximising engagement, visibility, and impact. The timing is also coordinated with the activities of other work packages, particularly those generating scientific, clinical, technological, or societal outcomes.

The timeframes outlined below are indicative and may be adjusted during the project to better align with actual progress, stakeholder feedback, and dissemination opportunities. This flexibility ensures that reporting obligations and strategic outreach remain responsive to evolving project and context dynamics.

CAMEL's dissemination and communication timeline is structured in **three main phases**:

1. Early Phase: Awareness and engagement (M1-12)

This initial phase focuses on laying the groundwork for effective dissemination by:

- Launching the project identity and communication tools (website, social media, templates);
- Establishing contact with key stakeholder groups (e.g., HCP, women's associations, policy networks);
- Promoting awareness of the project's objectives and expected outcomes;
- Initiating co-design and engagement activities;
- Sharing early insights on the project rationale and vision.

2. Core Phase: Results dissemination and feedback (M13-42)

As the project begins to generate intermediate results, this phase will emphasise:

- Dissemination of preliminary findings from clinical studies and co-creation processes;
- Promotion of the CVD Prevention Portal and app ecosystems as prototypes are released;
- Engagement of healthcare professionals and policy makers through conferences, webinars, and roundtables;
- Collection of feedback from target groups to refine tools and messaging;
- Cross-promotion through synergies and clustering activities with related EU projects.

This is the most dynamic and content-rich phase, requiring continuous adaptation of messaging and tools to reflect ongoing progress and stakeholder responses.

3. Final Phase: Capitalisation and sustainability (M43-60)

The final stage will be focused on maximising the long-term impact and policy uptake of CAMEL's results:

- Publication of final clinical and technological results;
- Launch of targeted policy briefs and strategic recommendations;

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- Dissemination of transferability and exploitation toolkits to support scale-up and uptake in diverse healthcare settings;
- Participation in EU policy forums and health innovation platforms;
- Showcasing of KERs to healthcare stakeholders as potential early adopters, regulators, and industry.

Throughout all phases, CAMEL will align its dissemination calendar with major scientific and public health events, awareness days (e.g., World Heart Day, Menopause Awareness Month), and relevant EC communication opportunities to ensure broader reach and resonance.

2.5 How to disseminate and communicate

The dissemination and communication strategy of CAMEL is built upon a multi-channel, audience-tailored approach designed to maximise impact, inclusivity, and uptake. Recognising the diversity of the project's stakeholder groups, CAMEL adopts a dynamic communication model that ensures key messages are adapted in tone, format, and language to resonate with the specific needs and preferences of each audience segment.

The communication and dissemination activities will be carried out through a combination of online and offline channels, owned media (e.g., website, project social media), earned media (e.g., media coverage, policy events), and partner channels (e.g., institutional platforms, newsletters, community networks). A strong emphasis is placed on visual identity, accessible design, and gender-sensitive language, in line with Horizon Europe guidelines.

To ensure operational clarity and coherence, the implementation of CDE activities will follow these core principles:

- **Audience-specific design:** Tools and content formats will be chosen based on the characteristics, behaviours, and literacy levels of each target group, as defined in Sections 2.2 and 2.7.
- **Strategic integration of channels:** Dissemination tools will not operate in isolation but in synergy, reinforcing each other through consistent messaging and cross-promotion (e.g., linking App content with social media posts and policy briefs).
- **Use of partners' networks:** All consortium partners will contribute to dissemination through their own institutional and professional channels, as defined in Section 3.7.
- **Evidence-based reach monitoring:** Data on social media followers, newsletter subscribers, and website analytics will be collected to support continuous evaluation and reporting. An initial mapping of existing reach (e.g., followers, networks) will be incorporated into the next iteration of the CDE Plan.
- **Flexible and iterative adaptation:** Communication approaches and tools will be regularly assessed and refined based on user feedback, performance indicators, and emerging dissemination opportunities (e.g., events, EU calls, awareness days).

Chapter 3 provides a detailed description of each dissemination tool and channel to be used for the CAMEL project, including visual identity, branded materials, digital presence, media outreach, and stakeholder engagement mechanisms.

Additionally, the consolidated communication mix matrix is presented, highlighting how the channels are smoothly aligned with the objectives, messages, and timing (Section 2.6).

2.6 Communication mix matrix

The table below provides an operational overview of CAMEL's communication and dissemination strategy, mapping the key objectives to target audiences, core messages, preferred channels, and timing.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Specific Objective	Target Group	General key messages	Channels & Tools	Timing
SO1: Develop novel, data-driven risk stratification models for menopausal women	Research community, HCPs	“CARMEL integrates AI and multimodal data for a new era of personalised CVD prevention.”	Scientific publications, webinars, technical factsheets, social media	M6-M60
SO2: Establish a modular digital ecosystem for women’s CVD prevention	Women 40–60, HCPs	“Self-assess your risk based on AI-powered analysis, access personalised advice, all in one digital platform.”	AsApp, Portal, videos, health fairs, social media	M12-M60
SO3: Generate real-world evidence through clinical studies	Healthcare professionals, General public, Policy makers & health authorities	“CARMEL is being tested in real-world settings across Europe and Latin America.”	Newsletters, press releases, events, policy briefs	M12-M48
SO4: Co-create tools with women, including those with intellectual disabilities	Women aged 40–60, Community health organizations	“CARMEL tools are built with real women’s voices, inclusive, accessible, and empowering.”	Focus groups, community events, workshops	M1-M36
SO5: Empower women and increase health literacy	Women 40–60, General public	“Know your heart. Know your risk. Prevention starts with awareness.”	Campaigns, brochures, influencers, local media	M6-M60
SO6: Support clinical and public health innovation	Policy makers and health authorities, HCPs	“Validated tools for gender-sensitive, preventive CVD care, to inform national guidelines and everyday clinical practice.”	Policy dialogues, white papers, health authority roundtables	M18-M60
SO7: Ensure long-term sustainability and exploitation of project results	Technology and innovation sector, policy makers, HCPs	“Validated, scalable, and regulation-ready innovations for digital prevention.”	B2B events, exploitation workshops, business model toolkit	M24-M60
SO8: Contribute to EU policies on women’s health and NCDs	Policy makers & health authorities, Community health organizations	“CARMEL brings actionable evidence and inclusive strategies to EU health agendas.”	EU health summits, position papers, clustering actions	M24-M60

Table 2 Communication mix matrix

2.7 Key messages tailored to target group

This Section outlines tailored key messages for each CAMEL target group, reflecting their specific needs, expectations, and roles in the project's success. Each subsection includes communication goals, appropriate tone, preferred channels, and a set of strategic messages aligned with CAMEL's objectives.

TG1. Healthcare professionals

Communication goal

Promote the clinical relevance, usability, and added value of CAMEL's digital tools and risk models for CVD personalised prevention, supporting their integration into everyday preventive care for women in midlife.

Tone and style

Professional, evidence-based, respectful of clinical expertise. Messages should highlight scientific robustness, real-world applicability, and ease of use within existing workflows.

Preferred channels

- Professional associations and newsletters.
- Medical conferences and symposia.
- Scientific journals and continuing medical education (CME) platforms.
- Hospital networks and internal communication tools.
- Webinars.
- Social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Youtube).

Key messages

1. Sex and gender sensitive prevention

- "Cardiovascular risk in women is often under-recognized, screen early, act early."
- "Integrate sex and gender specific approaches in diagnosis and treatment."
- "Empower midlife women with risk-based counselling and preventive care."
- "Transforming CVD risk management for menopausal women: CAMEL enhances early detection, stratification, and personalised management for women during and after menopause."
- "Bridge the gap: include more women in cardiovascular research and clinical trials."

2. AI-powered decision support

- "CAMEL offers validated, AI-driven models tailored to female physiology and multimodal data."
- "Discover CAMEL AI tools that support personalised care and informed clinical decisions."
- "CAMEL tools integrate seamlessly into clinical workflows, including EHRs."
- "Explore how digital biofeedback and wearable biosignals (e.g., breathing, heart rate) can inform preventive strategies."

3. Practice efficiency and innovation

- "The CAMEL tools reduce clinical workload by enabling remote monitoring of cardiovascular risk in large patient groups."
- "Enhance patient adherence and long-term outcomes with data-driven insights and educational content."
- "Integrate personalised lifestyle interventions directly into patient care."

4. Call to action

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- “Be part of a shift toward gender-sensitive, personalised preventive care.”
- “Collaborate with CAMEL to co-develop tools based on real-world data and clinical needs.”
- “Join a EU-wide effort to reduce gender bias in cardiovascular prevention and treatment.”
- “Your participation is vital to shaping innovative, equitable cardiovascular care.”
- “Help create the new standard for CVD risk assessment in midlife women.”

TG2. Women aged 40-60

Communication Goal

Empower women to take control of their cardiovascular health by raising awareness of sex and gender specific CVD risks, promoting the use of digital self-assessment tools, and encouraging participation in co-creation and clinical activities.

Tone and style

Reassuring, empathetic, accessible, and motivational. Language should be inclusive, non-technical, and sensitive to diverse backgrounds and health literacy levels, it should avoid medical jargon, and reflect the lived experiences of midlife women.

Preferred channels

- Social media (Facebook, YouTube).
- CAMEL App and Portal.
- Health-related blogs.
- Women’s magazines and local media.
- Community events and info sessions.
- Local media, influencers, and support groups.
- Collaboration with women’s health associations.

Key messages

1. Awareness and empowerment

- “Your heart health matters: midlife is the perfect time to take charge.”
- “Know your risk: menopause, stress, and lifestyle changes can impact your heart.”
- “Prevention is powerful: small steps like regular check-ups, balanced diet, and gentle exercise can make a big difference.”
- “Don’t ignore the signs! Heart disease can look different in women.”
- “Cardiovascular disease is the number one cause of death in women, but it’s preventable.”

2. Co-creation and participation

- “At CAMEL, your experience shapes the tools – we are co-creating digital health solutions with you, for you.”
- “Only with your participation can we create inclusive, effective tools for cardiovascular prevention.”
- “Your input is vital to build technologies that understand and respond to women’s needs.”
- “Join thousands of women shaping a new way to prevent heart disease, your voice matters.”
- “Whether you are tech-savvy or not, our App is designed with you, for you.”

3. Digital tools and support

- “Discover how innovation and wearable tech can support your well-being every day.”

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- “The CAMEL App helps you assess and manage cardiovascular risk, simply and safely.”
- “Biosignals like heart rate and breathing patterns can reveal early signs of stress, learn how to listen to your body.”

4. Inclusiveness and representation

- “CAMEL is for every woman, including those with special needs or limited access to care.”
- “We believe every woman deserves access to heart health, including those with special needs.”

5. Call to action

- "Be a health influencer in your family! Take care of yourself and inspire others."
- "Stay informed, stay empowered! CAMEL gives you the tools, you take the lead."

TG3. General public

Communication goal

Raise broad societal awareness about the importance of CVD prevention in women, challenging gender stereotypes and promoting supportive environments for healthy living and early detection.

Tone and style

Informative, inclusive, and awareness-raising. Messages should be easy to understand, focused on collective responsibility and social impact and with a lay language.

Preferred channels

- General media outlets (TV, radio, newspapers).
- Online media platforms and blogs.
- Public events and science festivals.
- Community organizations and local councils.
- Social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Youtube).

Key messages

1. Awareness and support

- “Heart disease is the number one killer of women. Awareness saves lives.”
- “Everyone has a role in preventing CVD. Support your loved ones to get screened.”
- “Be aware that women near you might experience over 15 symptoms during peri- and menopause. Listen and be supportive.”
- “Help us improve the cardiovascular health of the women around you. Share this message.”

2. Accessibility and equity

- “Women’s cardiovascular health has long been overlooked. CAMEL is working to change that.”
- “Health innovation is for everyone. CAMEL digital tools can make prevention smarter, fairer, and more accessible.”
- “CAMEL is developing solutions to support heart health in everyday life, for every woman.”

3. Daily habits and prevention

- “How we sit, move, or breathe can affect stress and heart health over time. Small changes matter.”
- “CAMEL explores how breathing and posture awareness can contribute to long-term wellness.”
- “The CAMEL tool helps women monitor their cardiovascular health and promotes everyday prevention.”

4. Technology for well-being

- “CAMEL technological innovations can help you care for your health in a safe and accessible way.”
- “Learn how CAMEL data and AI support more preventive and effective healthcare.”
- “CAMEL combines science and technology to protect women’s heart health during menopause.”

5. Call to action

- “The future of health is built with you. Get informed about CAMEL, get involved, and share.”
- “Follow CAMEL’s progress online and discover how to protect your heart and support those around you.”
- “Talk about menopause and heart health, and help CAMEL break the silence that surrounds women’s cardiovascular risk.”

TG5. Policy makers and health authorities

Communication goal

Promote the relevance of CAMEL as a model of evidence-based, gender-sensitive innovation in cardiovascular prevention, supporting informed policy-making, equitable health strategies, and the integration of digital tools into public health systems.

Tone and style

Institutional, formal, strategic, data-driven and impact-focused. Messages should highlight policy relevance, scalability, cost-effectiveness, and alignment with EU and national health priorities in digital and women’s health.

Preferred channels

- Policy briefs and white papers.
- Stakeholder roundtables and policy forums.
- Public health congresses and symposia.
- European Commission working groups and thematic clusters.
- Newsletters and targeted advocacy campaigns.

Key messages

1. Public health impact

- “CVD is the leading cause of death among women. Addressing it is a public health priority.”
- “Investing in women’s heart health reduces long-term healthcare costs and saves lives.”
- “We need healthy women for resilient health systems and thriving societies.”
- “CAMEL supports early detection and risk stratification, improving health outcomes at population level.”

2. Policy alignment and integration

- “CAMEL contributes to national and European priorities on digital innovation, gender equality, and preventive healthcare.”
- “Support national screening strategies and community-level outreach targeting midlife women.”
- “CAMEL tools can be scaled and integrated into national health programmes and electronic health records.”

3. Equity and inclusion

- “Prioritize gender-sensitive policies in cardiovascular prevention.”
- “CAMEL digital health platform empowers women to manage their health, access prevention tools, and improve menopause-related health literacy.”
- “CAMEL addresses access disparities by offering inclusive, user-friendly prevention solutions.”

4. Evidence-based innovation

- “CAMEL provides validated AI-driven models to support informed policy decisions and resource allocation.”
- “CAMEL supports evidence-based decision-making through advanced population data analysis.”
- “CAMEL technologies can help reduce healthcare costs and improve system efficiency.”
- “CAMEL lays the foundation for scalable digital prevention tools that can outlive the project and integrate into long-term health strategies.”

5. Call to action

- “Support research that helps close the gender gap in cardiovascular prevention.”
- “By endorsing CAMEL, you pave the way for sustainable, personalized prevention strategies.”
- “Let’s build together a more inclusive and cost-effective healthcare system for women.”

TG6. Research community

Communication goal

Foster interdisciplinary collaboration, promote the visibility and scalability of CAMEL’s scientific outputs, and encourage uptake, replication, and extension of its methodologies in sex and gender sensitive cardiovascular research.

Tone and style

Academic, technical, rigorous, forward-looking and open-science oriented. Messages should highlight methodological innovation and quality, data availability, scientific excellence, collaboration opportunities, the value of real-world data (RWD) and contribution to the European Research Area.

Preferred channels

- Peer-reviewed journals and open-access repositories.
- Scientific conferences, symposia, and workshops.
- Research networks and expert panels.
- EU research platform and cluster (e.g. Horizon Europe, COST Actions).
- Social media (LinkedIn).
- CAMEL dataset and model repositories (Zenodo).

Key messages

1. Closing knowledge gaps

- “Data gaps in women’s cardiovascular health hinder progress. Targeted research is critical.”
- “CARMEL generates high-quality real-world data on underrepresented female populations during menopause.”
- “Advance inclusive science with CARMEL: ensure diversity in study cohorts and represent real-world sex and age differences.”
- “We need research that serves real-world health needs and translates into clinical impact.”

2. Innovation through data and AI

- “CARMEL applies multimodal data and AI to improve cardiovascular prevention strategies.”
- “Collaborate on studies integrating big data, predictive models, and digital health tools.”
- “The CARMEL platform contributes to a RWD repository, available for research collaboration.”
- “CARMEL provide expertise in developing interoperable platforms and advanced analytics for studies and clinical trials.”

3. Interdisciplinary collaboration

- “CARMEL invites clinicians, data scientists, social scientists, and gender researchers to co-create evidence-based prevention strategies.”
- “CARMEL foster multidisciplinary synergies to accelerate knowledge transfer and societal impact.”
- “Partner with CARMEL to validate findings, explore novel diagnostics, and expand the research agenda on women’s cardiovascular health.”

4. Scientific excellence and dissemination

- “CARMEL ensures methodological rigor and clinical relevance in all study phases.”
- “CARMEL promote open science: publications, presentations, and data are accessible via Zenodo and project platforms.”
- “Contribute to a shared effort with CARMEL to reshape cardiovascular research around gender and life-course perspectives.”

5. Call to action

- “Join a European initiative at the frontier of digital health and women’s cardiovascular prevention.”
- “Collaborate with CARMEL to expand the evidence base and inform future clinical and public health practice.”
- “Let’s close the gender gap in cardiovascular research together.”
- “Fuel scientific advancement with CARMEL!”

TG7. Technology and innovation sector

Communication goal

Promote CARMEL’s digital outputs as exploitable innovations, foster partnerships for scale-up and commercialisation, and position the project as an AI-powered solution that addresses gender-specific needs and has real-world impact in preventive healthcare.

Tone and style

Business- and solution-oriented, innovation-driven, opportunity-focused, collaborative. Messages should highlight technological readiness, market and business potential, alignment with digital health trends and regulatory frameworks, scalability and potential for integration.

Preferred channels

- Industry events and innovation summits.
- Innovation networks and clusters (e.g., EIT Health, Digital Europe).
- Webinars, tech blogs, and product showcases.
- Social media (Linkedin, Youtube).
- EU innovation matchmaking events, brokerage events and B2B meetings.

Key messages

1. Innovating cardiovascular prevention

- “CARMEL’s innovation in digital health and wearables can transform cardiovascular care for women.”
- “Women need tailored strategies for better heart health. Self-management tools are key to enabling this shift.”
- “CARMEL integrates cutting-edge AI, wearable tech, and digital health to reimagine prevention.”
- “Join CARMEL in co-designing tech that responds to the real-world needs of women during and after menopause.”

2. Smart systems and data-driven design

- “CARMEL draws from wearable sensing and real-time feedback to explore how micro-behaviors influence cardiovascular risk.”
- “Edge computing and on-body data streams are critical to building responsive, user-centered health tools.”
- “The CARMEL App enables women to monitor health, wellbeing, and risk across different life stages.”
- “CARMEL designs technology with female-specific data, needs, and lived experiences in mind.”

3. Scalability, security, and integration

- “CARMEL develops scalable and secure digital health solutions using AI, edge computing, and data analytics.”
- “CARMEL creates interoperable tools that can integrate into larger digital health ecosystems.”
- “Innovation at the intersection of clinical relevance and technical feasibility is central to CARMEL’s approach.”

4. Collaboration opportunities

- “Partner with CARMEL to build scalable AI-driven solutions with real-world health impact.”
- “Explore joint innovation pathways to transform preventive care and women's health outcomes.”
- “CARMEL is a living lab for digital health innovation: test, iterate, and co-develop breakthrough features.”

5. Call to action

- “The future of healthcare innovation is here. Let’s build it together with CARMEL.”
- “Collaborate with CARMEL’s next-generation digital health solutions that put women’s cardiovascular health at the center.”
- “Join a EU-wide initiative shaping smarter, more inclusive digital health technologies.”

TG8. Community health organizations

Communication goal

Mobilise local health actors to promote gender-sensitive cardiovascular prevention, support the dissemination and contextualisation of CAMEL tools, and co-develop inclusive strategies to reach underserved women during the menopausal transition, including women with intellectual disabilities.

Tone and style

Empowering, inclusive, community-oriented, collaborative. Messages should focus on accessibility and collaboration, be practical and culturally sensitive, highlighting real-world relevance, shared values, and the potential to improve health equity through local engagement.

Preferred channels

- Workshops and community events.
- Partnerships with NGOs, advocacy groups, and local health networks.
- Informational kits and printable materials.
- Newsletters, and local media.
- Community ambassadors and peer educators.
- Social media (Linkedin, Facebook Youtube).

Key messages

1. Local leadership and trust

- “You are trusted messengers. Help spread awareness about heart health in women.”
- “Community-based interventions can close equity gaps in cardiovascular prevention.”
- “Partner with clinics and local leaders to reach underserved midlife women.”
- “CAMEL recognises the key role of community actors in building healthier futures.”

2. Accessible and inclusive prevention

- “CAMEL offers a digital platform to help women monitor their health, lifestyle, and cardiovascular risk.”
- “CAMEL investigates how simple feedback, like breathing reminders, can support sustainable healthy habits.”
- “CAMEL offers digital tools that support your work in health education, engagement, and local empowerment.”
- “Adapt prevention strategies to real-world contexts and the needs of diverse communities.”

3. Collaboration and co-design

- “Collaborate to ensure our tools are inclusive, practical, and impactful in local settings.”
- “CAMEL’s solutions are co-designed with and for the people they serve.”
- “We welcome your input to shape outreach strategies and promote equitable access.”
- “Help tailor our resources to resonate with your mission, your members, and your realities.”

4. Shared values and impact

- “Supporting women’s heart health strengthens families, communities, and futures.”
- “Menopause is a natural transition. Let’s promote knowledge, not fear.”
- “Your participation is truly valuable to the success of this initiative.”
- “Together, we can amplify impact where it matters most.”

5. Call to action

- “Collaborate with CAMEL to bring personalised prevention to the women in your community.”

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- “Use and share our evidence-based tools to support women’s cardiovascular health.”
- “Help us improve the heart health of women around you. Share this message.”

2.8 Dissemination obligations and rules

The CAMEL CDE plan is grounded in the legal obligations defined in the Grant Agreement. These obligations ensure transparency, open access, and visibility of EU funding, while supporting coherent, inclusive, and ethical communication throughout the project’s lifetime. Compliance with these rules contributes directly to the project’s core values, including gender sensitivity, inclusiveness, scientific openness, and ethical responsibility. All project partners are expected to adhere to these rules when producing or approving dissemination materials related to CAMEL.

The table below summarises the key obligations and rules applicable to CAMEL.

Obligations/ Rules	Descriptions and references	Implementation in CAMEL
Promotion of the action and its results	Beneficiaries must promote the action and its results in a strategic, coherent and effective manner to multiple audiences (media, public, stakeholders). Major media-impact activities must be pre-notified to the granting authority. Reference: GA, Art. 17.1	Communication activities are coordinated by WP14 following the CDE strategy outlined in Chapter 2. Major impact actions will be flagged and communicated to the granting authority as needed.
Visibility of EU support	All dissemination and communication materials must display the EU emblem and the statement: “Funded by the European Union.” Reference: GA, Art. 17.2	The visual identity package developed in WP14 (see Section 3.1) includes compliant templates. All partners are required to use them.
Use of disclaimer	All activities must include the disclaimer: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only...”. Reference: GA, Art. 17.3	The disclaimer is embedded in all the templates. WP14 Leader and the Project Coordinator ensure this is consistently applied in all outputs.
Accuracy of information	Communications must use factually accurate and non-misleading information. Reference: GA, Art. 17.3	All content is subject to internal review. Technical content is validated by leading WPs; final approval by WP14 Leader and Project Coordinator.
Open access to scientific publications	Peer-reviewed publications must be deposited in an open-access repository and made freely available. Reference: GA, Art. 16	CAMEL will use Zenodo for publication deposits.
Protection of results and prior notice	Beneficiaries must inform the consortium before disseminating results, to allow assessment of potential intellectual property or confidentiality issues. Reference: GA, Art. 16	Internal procedures reflecting the Grant Agreement are included in the Consortium Agreement and in the Project Management Handbook (D1.1) and require partners to notify WP14 Leader, Project Coordinator and affected WPs at least 30 days before publication or presentation.

Obligations/ Rules	Descriptions and references	Implementation in CAMEL
Respect for ethics and privacy	All dissemination must comply with GDPR and ethical standards, particularly regarding sensitive data and vulnerable populations. Reference: GDPR (EU) 2016/679;	WP14 Leader coordinates with Project Coordinator and TIMELEX, as legal expert, for review of dissemination materials. Eventually, some issued might be brought to the attention of the Gender, Ethics, Legal, and Data access Committee (GLED)
Inclusive and gender-sensitive language	Language must be inclusive and adapted to the literacy levels of different audiences, reflecting Horizon Europe's equality principles. Reference: Horizon Europe Communication Guidelines on Gender and Inclusiveness	WP14 applies plain language principles and inclusive design. Researchers from all partners will be briefed by M6 in the gender in research aspects following training programme designed and delivered by TCD partner, publicly available in CAMEL project website.

Table 3 CAMEL CDE rules and obligations

2.9 Internal coordination of dissemination activities

To ensure the coherence, efficiency, and timely implementation of all CDE activities, the CAMEL project has established a structured mechanism for internal coordination and partner engagement.

A dedicated **WP14 coordination call** is held every two weeks, bringing together the partners responsible for the leadership of the WP14 tasks. These meetings are used to plan upcoming actions, monitor the status of deliverables and campaign materials, review performance indicators, and align on external opportunities such as events, publications, or EU-level initiatives. The same coordination call will be established during WP15 and WP16 to ensure continuity.

In addition, the **Technical Management Team (TMT)**, organized by the coordinator and composed of WP leaders and key project representatives, meets bi-weekly and serves as an additional platform for cross-WP alignment. During TMT meetings, WP14 provides updates on CDE strategy and tools, and collects inputs from other WPs to feed into the dissemination pipeline.

All dissemination materials, including social media toolkits, press releases, visual assets, templates, and news items, are shared with the consortium via the Microsoft Teams platform. Partners are encouraged to:

- Contribute actively to content creation;
- Repost and amplify official CAMEL messages through their own channels;
- Engage their networks in dissemination campaigns;
- Provide feedback on the usability and uptake of communication tools.

Whenever needed, and particularly for sensitive or context-specific materials, draft dissemination content is reviewed by the consortium or by relevant partners, for example, clinical sites when materials concern WP4 activities, as well as TIMELEX and DCU as legal and Ethics experts. This process helps ensure that communication is effective, inclusive, and

free from unintended biases, and that both textual and visual elements are accurate, appropriate, and aligned with stakeholder expectations.

If specific needs or opportunities arise (e.g., local campaigns, urgent media requests, stakeholder crises, or context-sensitive topics), dedicated ad-hoc coordination activities are launched as required.

This internal coordination and validation framework supports a coherent, responsive, and partner-driven dissemination strategy, ensuring that CARMEL's messages are consistently aligned, widely diffused, and co-owned by the entire consortium.

3. Dissemination and communication tools and channels

This Chapter presents the set of tools and channels that will be used to implement CARMEL's communication and dissemination strategy. These tools are designed to support the delivery of audience-specific messages in ways that are accessible, inclusive, and aligned with the project's scientific vision and visual identity.

The selected tools cover a wide range of formats and media, both digital and physical, and are mapped to the project's objectives, target audiences, and communication phases as outlined in Chapter 2. They include CARMEL's visual identity elements, branded materials (such as brochures, slide decks, posters), digital infrastructure (the website and the CVD prevention portal), media outreach (press releases, social media, newsletter) scientific publications, and participation in events and clustering activities. Each tool is selected and adapted to match the audience's characteristics, the nature of the content, and the phase of the project lifecycle.

All tools and channels will be **continuously updated and evaluated** to ensure consistency, inclusiveness, and impact. The implementation of these tools is coordinated by WP14, with the active involvement of all partners through a shared communication system, as described in Section 2.9. A dedicated sub-chapter also presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used to monitor and evaluate the reach, engagement, and impact of CARMEL's communication and dissemination actions, ensuring their continuous improvement and alignment with Horizon Europe expectations.

3.1 CARMEL visual identity

3.1.1 CARMEL logo

The CARMEL logo has been designed by VICOM to reflect the project's innovative and inclusive identity through a clean, symbolic, and adaptable visual language. The logotype is based on a creative interplay between the letters "C" and "A" from the project name, forming a distinctive isotype. Visually, the shape also resembles a wrapped candy, suggesting care and accessibility, qualities that align with the project's human-centred and empowering approach to support women.

To ensure optimal versatility, the logo has been developed in both horizontal and vertical formats, and follows responsive design principles to maintain its clarity and proportions across various media.

Figure 1 CARMEL logo, vertical and horizontal

The original logo colour palette consists of four core tones:

- **Black** (#000000)
- **Dark Red** (#E61F26)
- **Salmon Pink** (#FF6666)
- **White** (#FFFFFF)

To enhance design flexibility and accommodate diverse formats and thematic contexts, the project adopted an **extended palette** that includes:

- **Charcoal Blue** (#253847)
- **Plum Burgundy** (#4a0036)
- **Deep Teal Blue** (#004e72)
- **Pale Sky Blue** (#ccf6ff)
- **Steel Blue** (#527c96)

In addition to the primary logo, selected graphic elements derived from the logotype, such as geometric shapes extracted from the letters “C” and “A”, are used throughout both digital and print materials. These modular elements (Fig. 2) serve as recurring visual motifs across the project’s templates, promotional items, and online presence, helping to reinforce brand identity in a subtle yet distinctive way.

Figure 2 CARMEL modular elements

Together, these visual elements ensure consistency and recognisability across all CARMEL communication materials, while allowing for sufficient adaptability to reach diverse audiences through engaging, inclusive design.

The CARMEL logo must be used on all dissemination and communication materials produced within the project. It should always appear in high quality and in a prominent position, ensuring immediate recognition of the project identity. Correct application of the logo includes maintaining sufficient clear space and using approved formats to preserve visual coherence across all platforms and media.

3.1.2 Templates

From the outset of the CARMEL project, dedicated branded templates have been created to ensure visual consistency and recognition across all dissemination and communication outputs. These templates are crucial for aligning materials with the project's visual identity and enhancing the professional presentation of CARMEL's work.

Three main templates have been developed:

- A **PowerPoint template**, used for presentations at project meetings, conferences, and public events; it includes the graphic motifs derived from the CARMEL logo, already introduced in the previous paragraph, which appear along the side of the slides, adding visual continuity across all dissemination formats without distracting from the content;
- A **letterhead template**, used for official correspondence;
- A **Word template**, used for deliverables and technical documentation.

All templates include mandatory EU funding acknowledgment and comply with Horizon Europe visibility requirements (described in chapter 2.8) and they are shared with all partners via the internal platform.

The following screenshots provide examples of the official PowerPoint template in use:

Figure 3 CARMEL presentations template

Additional figures below illustrate the official letterhead and Word deliverable templates.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Figure 4 CARMEL Letterhead

Figure 5 CARMEL Documents template

3.1.3 Presentation – Slide deck

A standard project presentation was developed by the project coordinator VICOM during the early stages of CARMEL, using the official slide template described above. This PowerPoint slide deck serves as a shared reference tool and is used to ensure consistent representation of the project at external events, conferences, stakeholder meetings, and institutional briefings. The presentation provides a structured overview of the project's challenges, objectives, methodology, clinical studies, and KERs.

Below are selected screenshots from the official project presentation:

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Figure 6 Slides from the CARMEL project presentation

3.2 Website

The CARMEL website serves as the project's central digital communication hub, providing accessible and up-to-date information. It plays a key role in ensuring the visibility, transparency, and outreach of the project throughout its duration. The website was officially launched in Month 4 (M4) and is available at: www.caramel-project.eu. A comprehensive overview of the site's structure, functions, and target audiences is provided in **D14.2 Project Website**.

As the project evolves, the website will be continuously updated to reflect new milestones, findings, publications, and stakeholder engagement opportunities. This ensures that the platform remains a living, dynamic space for dissemination and interaction.

To foster continuous engagement, the website includes a dedicated contact form that allows visitors to:

- Subscribe to the project newsletter, to receive regular updates on progress, events, and results;
- Express their interest in becoming a project stakeholder, thus joining the CARMEL community and being informed about co-creation activities, events, and collaboration opportunities.

Below is a screenshot of the website homepage:

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

CAMEL
Cardiovascular Risk Assessment via multimodal data analysis enabling personalised prevention strategies targeting MENopausal women

Home About Gender Training Resources News Contact us

Empowering women's heart health in menopause with a personalised cardiovascular risk prevention

CAMEL is a research and innovation project funded under Horizon Europe. It aims to develop an AI-driven, personalized prevention model tailored to the unique cardiovascular health needs of women aged 40-60, particularly during the menopausal transition, when CVD risk rises significantly. CAMEL will empower women to better understand their cardiovascular health and adopt effective prevention strategies, ensuring they receive the attention and care they deserve during this critical life stage.

More info

CAMEL in numbers

- 5 Years
- 25 Partners
- 11 Countries
- 6 Clinical sites
- 6.000 Women involved

Latest news from CAMEL project

- CAMEL Kick-Off Meeting Of The External Advisory Board**
21/05/2025
On 21 May 2025, the CAMEL project formally launched its collaboration with the External Advisory Board (EAB), a milestone moment that brings strategic oversight and independent expertise to the heart of the project's mission. [...]
- CAMEL Is Officially On Zenodo**
30/04/2025
We are excited to announce that the CAMEL project is now officially available on Zenodo: the open-access platform supported by the European Commission. This reflects CAMEL's strong commitment to transparency, scientific openness, and full [...]
- CAMEL's Mixed Method Study Begins**
31/03/2025
CAMEL is pleased to announce the launch of a large-scale study aimed at assessing cardiovascular risk factors in women aged 40 to 60, particularly during the menopausal transition. The study, involving leading research and [...]

More news

Stay connected with CAMEL

Want to get involved? Join our network of stakeholders and help advance innovative solutions for heart health. Sign up for our newsletter to receive updates on CAMEL's work.

- Subscribe to the newsletter
- Join as a stakeholder

you@example.com *

I have read and agree to the Privacy policy

Submit

Our Consortium

Get to know us

CONTACTS
Project Coordinator
Idan Macia
Fundación Centro de Tecnologías de Interacción Visual y Comunicaciones
Vicotech
Project Email
info@caramel-project.eu

FOLLOW US
f z b in

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101156210. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible.

© 2025 - Caramel project - All Rights Reserved - Illustrations by Freepik - FlatIcon - Made by Social IT - Privacy Policy - Terms of use and Cookies Policy

Figure 7 CAMEL project website homepage

3.3 CAMEL branded materials

3.3.1 CAMEL brochure

A project brochure has been developed to provide a concise and visually engaging overview of the CAMEL project. Designed as a trifold leaflet, it serves as a key communication tool for use in public events, conferences, stakeholder meetings, and institutional outreach. The brochure introduces the project's challenges, core objectives, methodology, clinical studies, and the digital solutions being developed. It is available in English and has been translated into the languages of the Consortium partners (Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, Lithuanian, Croatian, Finnish, Hebrew, French and Italian), to support local engagement and enhance the accessibility of key messages.

Two screenshots of the official brochure are shown below:

Figure 8 CAMEL brochure

3.3.2 Poster

An official project poster has been created to visually present the CAMEL project in a concise and accessible format. Designed for use at conferences, public events, and stakeholder meetings, the poster summarises the project's challenge, objectives, methodology, and timeline. It follows the CAMEL visual identity and has been translated into all partner languages (see list in the above paragraph) to ensure consistency and accessibility across countries.

A preview of the official project poster is shown below:

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Figure 9 CARMEL poster

3.3.3 Roll-up

An official roll-up banner has been produced to support the CARMEL project's visibility at public events, conferences, and institutional venues. Designed in alignment with the project's visual identity, the roll-up offers a quick visual summary of CARMEL's mission and objectives. It complements other branded materials such as the brochure and poster and has been produced in English.

A visual preview of the roll-up banner is presented below:

Figure 10 CARMEL roll-up

3.3.4 Videos

Video content is an essential component of CAMEL’s communication and engagement strategy. It supports awareness-raising, accessibility, and emotional connection with diverse audiences through a visual and inclusive narrative. As foreseen in the project plan, two institutional videos will be produced, one at the start and one at the end of the project:

The first video already produced and titled “CAMEL: A new path to heart health for women” introduces the project’s goals, the unmet needs in cardiovascular prevention for women aged 40–60, CAMEL’s AI-driven and inclusive approach, and the role of the European Union in supporting this initiative.

The second video, to be released in the final project phase, will highlight results and impacts, with a strong visual focus on inclusivity and featuring real testimonials from women and clinicians participating in the clinical studies.

In addition, four training videos will be developed linked to the CVD Prevention Portal. These will cover key topics including: CVD prevention in women and gender disparities, AI for personalised prevention, self-management, and clinical digital skills

The first video is already published on the project’s YouTube channel and is available at this link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rThmU1ZWq7o&ab_channel=CaramelProject.

Some preview still from the video are shown below:

Figure 11 Stills from CAMEL video

3.4 Press releases

Press releases are an integral part of CAMEL’s dissemination strategy, used to communicate key milestones and engage wider audiences through mainstream and specialised media channels. As outlined in the project proposal, a media brief was prepared for the kick-off of the project and adapted for use by all partners to ensure consistent, clear messaging about the project’s goals and societal relevance. Press releases are issued on an

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

as-needed basis, with a focus on strategic moments such as the launch of the clinical studies and the release of policy recommendations.

To date, two official press releases have been published:

- The first, at the project's kick-off, introduced CAMEL's mission, consortium, and focus on cardiovascular disease prevention in women aged 40–60;
- The second, launched alongside the T4.1 activities, announced the public survey aimed at mapping women's experiences, perceptions, and needs regarding heart health during the menopause transition.

Press releases are drafted by SIT and then shared with all partners, who are encouraged to translate and adapt them to their local contexts in order to maximise outreach and relevance. Partners are also advised to distribute them through local and national media channels. All press releases are published on the official CAMEL website to ensure accessibility and long-term visibility.

3.5 Newsletters

As outlined in the project proposal, a digital newsletter will be published regularly throughout the project to keep general public and stakeholders informed about CAMEL's progress, upcoming events, publications, and key achievements. A total of 8 issues are planned over the course of the project. The newsletter will be issued with Mailchimp and distributed to subscribers who have voluntarily opted in and provided their consent via the project website, in full compliance with GDPR regulations, and promoted across CAMEL's official social media channels to extend its visibility and engagement reach. Each issue will feature updates on scientific developments, news from the clinical sites, opportunities for engagement, and relevant events.

All newsletters will be drafted by SIT, and partners are encouraged to contribute content and promote the issues within their networks. This collaborative approach helps maintain relevance across languages and local contexts, with partners also encouraged to translate key newsletter highlights where appropriate and disseminate. All newsletter editions will be publicly accessible via the CAMEL project website and archived to allow continuous access to project developments.

3.6 Social media channels

CAMEL's social media strategy is an essential component of its outreach and stakeholder engagement framework. Informed by the project's communication goals and target audiences, social media channels are used to disseminate timely updates, promote events and results, foster dialogue with stakeholders, and raise public awareness on the gender-specific dimensions of cardiovascular health.

The official CAMEL social media accounts are:

- **Facebook:** facebook.com/caramelproject
- **LinkedIn:** linkedin.com/company/caramel-project
- **YouTube:** youtube.com/@caramel_project

While the original proposal foresaw the use of Twitter, the consortium strategically opted for Facebook during the project's implementation phase. This decision was based on a data-driven assessment of audience preferences, recognising Facebook's stronger relevance and accessibility for the project's primary target group, women aged 40–60, who are significantly more active on this platform. In addition to Facebook, the project leverages LinkedIn to engage healthcare professionals, researchers, and institutional stakeholders, while YouTube is used to publish accessible video content.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Each platform is managed by SIT following a collaborative approach. During the initial phases, content is primarily developed by SIT, with partners invited to contribute progressively as their work packages produce outputs. This includes scientific insights, co-creation milestones, clinical updates, and engagement activities. All posts include the required EU and CAMEL branding, as required by the GA, ensuring visual consistency and alignment with Horizon Europe communication standards. All partners are expected to actively amplify project visibility by sharing official content on their institutional channels.

To ensure brand coherence and visual impact across platforms, a dedicated cover image has been developed for each social media channel. These covers are fully aligned with the visual identity described in Section 3.1 and reinforce CAMEL's recognisability and professional presentation.

Below are screenshots of the official CAMEL social media profiles:

Figure 12 CAMEL LinkedIn account

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Figure 13 CAMEL Facebook Account

Figure 14 CAMEL YouTube Account

To ensure recognisability and consistency, each post includes a set of fixed hashtags supplemented by topic-specific tags to enhance discoverability. Here is the list of the fixed hashtags:

- #CAMELproject
- #HorizonEurope
- #EuropeanProject
- #CardiovascularHealth
- #Innovation
- #AI
- #ArtificialIntelligence
- #InnovationForHealth
- #WomensHealth
- #PersonalizedMedicine

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- #CVDPrevention
- #DigitalHealth
- #PreventionMatters
- #HealthcareInnovation
- #HorizonEU
- #HeartHealth
- #WomenInHealth

The social media activity will be continuously monitored through KPIs defined in the project proposal (detailed Section 4.1), including growth in followers, engagement metrics, and referral traffic to the project website.

In cases where specific communication needs arise, such as reaching targeted audiences or promoting localised actions, ad hoc posts are created with tailored text and visuals that partners can directly share on their institutional channels. These targeted materials are designed to maximise outreach and contextual relevance, ensuring high visibility and alignment with the project's identity.

When necessary, SIT provides complete content packages that include:

- **English text drafts**, which are translated by the partner into their local language;
- **Visual materials**, created using Canva, which can be:
 - directly adapted by partners if they have the capacity to edit visuals in-house;
 - or translated collaboratively, with partners supplying translated text elements and SIT delivering the final customised visual.

All posts include the required EU and CAMEL branding, and when disseminated by a specific partner, their institutional logo is also integrated into the visual to strengthen ownership and local engagement. This flexible approach was successfully applied during the dissemination of the T4.1 survey, in which TCD and all clinical partners played an active role. This model ensures agile and context-sensitive dissemination, while maintaining visual consistency and compliance with Horizon Europe visibility requirements.

3.7 Partners communication tools and channels

In addition to the centralised tools managed by SIT, each consortium partner contributes to the project's dissemination and communication efforts through their own institutional and professional channels. These may include institutional websites, social media accounts, newsletters, blogs, mailing lists, and participation in external events or conferences.

Leveraging partner-owned tools and networks is key to amplifying the reach and visibility of CAMEL, ensuring that messages are disseminated across diverse sectors, geographies, and stakeholder groups. It also supports localisation of content and allows partners to engage directly with their communities, ecosystems, and national audiences in their respective languages and contexts.

3.8 CAMEL CVD Prevention Portal

The CVD Prevention Portal (hereinafter the Portal) will be developed as a central component of CAMEL's digital ecosystem, designed to support women aged 40–60 in understanding, assessing, and managing their cardiovascular risk. Conceived as an accessible, web-based interface, the Portal will offer personalised prevention pathways, evidence-based information, and digital health resources tailored to the specific needs of midlife women. The Portal will be closely connected with the CAMEL App ecosystem (currently being developed in WP9), providing complementary functionalities and ensuring continuity across web and mobile platforms. Its design will draw upon international best practices in accessibility, usability, and

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

gender-sensitive digital health. Particular attention will be given to the needs of women with intellectual disabilities, in line with the inclusive vision of CAMEL.

The Portal will serve as both an engagement and dissemination tool, supporting CAMEL's broader strategy of outreach, empowerment, and uptake. It will act as a transversal enabler, contributing to multiple dimensions of the project, including communication, feasibility validation, and long-term sustainability.

The main TGs of the Portal are:

- **Women aged 40–60**, the primary end-users, including both study participants and the broader public reached through engagement activities;
- **Healthcare professionals**, who may recommend the Portal as a reliable resource and use it to support patient counselling;
- **Policy and public health stakeholders**, who may be interested in digital prevention tools for integration into wider health promotion strategies.

The Portal will be fully integrated into CAMEL's broader communication and dissemination ecosystem, serving as a central interface for public engagement and personalised cardiovascular prevention. As such, its visibility will be strategically supported through a mix of online and offline tools and channels (as described in this Chapter), ensuring coherence in messaging and alignment with the needs of different stakeholder groups.

The dissemination of the Portal will aim to:

- Position it as a key resource within the CAMEL digital ecosystem;
- Attract and retain user engagement, particularly among women aged 40–60;
- Reinforce its complementarity with the CAMEL App suite and training materials;
- Ensure accessibility and inclusion, especially for women with intellectual disabilities.

Dissemination efforts will be progressively intensified as the Portal nears completion. KPIs linked to the Portal, such as page views and self-assessment completions, are detailed in Section 4.1. These metrics will serve to monitor user engagement, refine the user experience, and assess the Portal's contribution to the project's broader impact objectives.

The Portal will be developed by SIT with DCU, as Task leader of Task 14.2. The Portal will be available by M18 and further populated in WP15 and WP16.

3.9 Publications

Scientific publications represent a central pillar of CAMEL's dissemination strategy. They serve to ensure the visibility, credibility, and scientific impact of the project's results, while contributing to the broader advancement of gender-sensitive cardiovascular research, digital health innovation, and AI-based prevention models.

CAMEL distinguishes between two types of publication outputs:

- **Public deliverables**, which are published on the project's Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/caramelproject/>), ensuring open access to key project documentation, as required by Article 16 and Annex 5 of the GA;
- **Scientific publications**, which refer to peer-reviewed articles, conference proceedings, and symposia contributions authored by project partners and submitted to high-impact journals and academic venues.

The **Zenodo** account has been established by the Coordinator, and access has been granted to SIT to support coordinated uploading and tagging. All partners are required to respect EU visibility and open access obligations, ensuring that publications are deposited with appropriate metadata, licensing (CC BY 4.0), and project references, in line with Horizon Europe guidelines.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

Internal collaboration is strongly encouraged in the development of scientific articles. Partners are invited to co-author publications resulting from cross-WP activities, clinical research findings, or methodological innovations. This collaborative model enhances the scientific value of the outputs and fosters knowledge exchange across disciplines and countries.

Based on the project's thematic scope, the following journals, conferences and congress have been preliminary identified as strategic publication targets:

Journals:

- Maturitas;
- European Journal of Heart Failure;
- European Heart Journal (European Society of Cardiology);
- American Journal of Cardiology;
- Journal of Women's Health;
- JACC: Heart Failure;
- Circulation (American Heart Association);
- Circulation: Heart Failure;
- International Journal of Medical Informatics;
- ESC Heart Failure;
- BMJ Open.

Conferences:

- European Society of Cardiology (ESC);
- European Heart Rhythm Association (EHRA);
- Computing in Cardiology (CiC);
- European Stroke Organization Conference (ESOC);
- Functional Imaging and modelling of the Heart (FIMH);
- Society of Cardiac Computed Tomography (SCCT) Global Meeting;
- Congenital, Structural and valvar heart disease Interventions (CSI);
- International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI);
- European Congress of Menopause and Andropause (EMAS);
- Panhellenic Cardiology Congress;
- Panhellenic Scientific Conference of Obstetrics and Gynecology;
- International Society of Gynecological Endocrinology (ISGE) Congress.

Additional journals and conferences may be identified throughout the project based on the nature of the results and evolving publication opportunities. The project aims to produce a minimum of 20 peer-reviewed scientific publications during its lifetime.

More than ten partners have already initiated planning for scientific publications. The proposed topics include: a position paper on CAMEL, the study protocol, findings from remote patient monitoring, AI-driven models for CV-RA, the design and implementation of the CAMEL Digital Platform, as well as reviews on CVD self-assessment tools and lifestyle apps targeting women aged 40–60 or experiencing menopause. Additional publications are expected to emerge as the project progresses and further results become available.

Publications will be reported in the continuous reporting module of SYGMA and within the Periodic Reports.

3.10 Networking and clustering activities

Networking and clustering activities are a core element of CAMEL's dissemination and engagement strategy. These actions are designed to increase the project's visibility, facilitate

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

the exchange of knowledge with related initiatives, and foster strategic alliances that support the long-term uptake and sustainability of project outcomes.

To systematise this effort and ensure consistency across the consortium, relevant information was collected from all partners regarding:

- **Related projects:** national or international research and innovation projects aligned with CAMEL's objectives;
- **Established networks and platforms:** memberships or affiliations with thematic networks and alliances relevant to women's health, cardiovascular research, digital health, and AI for CVD prevention;
- **Stakeholders:** identified organisations or institutions, from clinical, academic, policy, industry or civil society domains relevant to CAMEL's implementation and impact;
- **External events:** conferences, workshops, webinars or roundtables where CAMEL could be presented or strategically promoted;
- **Partner-organised events:** institutional events or initiatives organized by the partners where they plan to include or feature the CAMEL project;
- **CAMEL-led events:** events to be hosted by the consortium during the project's lifecycle.

Each partner populated the template with available data, drawing on their own networks and institutional contexts. The inputs were then consolidated into a single shared file, creating a comprehensive **CAMEL Networking and Clustering Database**, which will be regularly updated throughout the project's lifecycle by the whole Consortium. This resource will provide a real-time overview of emerging opportunities, ensure efficient coordination of outreach efforts, and serve as an operational tool to monitor and expand the project's ecosystem of collaboration.

The following Sections outline CAMEL's networking and clustering activities.

3.10.1 Synergies with related projects

Establishing synergies with other European and international initiatives is a key strategy within CAMEL's dissemination and sustainability framework. These synergies are seen not only as opportunities for mutual learning and joint dissemination, but also as a foundation for scaling and transferring CAMEL's models, tools, and co-design practices across different contexts and user groups.

To support this strategic effort, project partners have identified a wide range of ongoing and completed initiatives relevant to CAMEL. These include Horizon Europe, national programmes, and European partnerships working on: cardiovascular risk assessment and management; AI and big data in personalised medicine; digital tools for health empowerment and self-management; women's health and gendered innovations; patient engagement and health equity.

A particular focus is placed on synergies with sister projects funded by the same topic where CAMEL was funded (HORIZON-HLTH-2024-STAYHLTH-01-05-two-stage - Personalised prevention of non-communicable diseases - addressing areas of unmet needs using multiple data sources) which address interconnected health challenges such as cardiovascular prevention, AI-enabled diagnostics, and personalised care. Coordinated actions with these projects, such as joint dissemination or clustering events, will strengthen the visibility and impact of the overall research efforts, as well as contribute to a cohesive policy dialogue. The following Table provides an overview of the sister projects.

Project	Objectives
DORIAN GRAY – Devising a personalized risk stratification and holistic management for prevention of cognitive impairment in patients with different cardiovascular phenotypes	To delay CVD-related cognitive impairment through AI-powered digital twins and multidomain interventions
PerPrev-CID – PERsonalized disease prediction and PREvention in Chronic Inflammatory Disorders	To improve prevention in RA and IBD via biomarkers, digital health tools, and nutrition-based interventions
SHIELD – Strategic Health Initiatives for Effective Disease Prevention	To prevent CVD and diabetes using AI-based personalised risk stratification and digital monitoring tools

Table 2 CAMEL sister projects

An initial contact with sister projects and discussion about potential synergies, already took in Coordinators Meeting by HADEA in March 13. The setup of work groups for specific thematic areas such as data sharing, joint dissemination, engagement in clinical trials FAIR-ification of data were discussed and will follow in the next months.

A broader set of related projects identified by the consortium partners is presented in Appendix I and will be continuously updated to reflect ongoing engagements and emerging synergies. Throughout the project's duration, CAMEL partners will actively seek out new synergies with relevant initiatives, aiming to enhance visibility, share resources, and amplify the collective impact of gender-sensitive, AI-driven health innovation.

3.10.2 Networks

A preliminary mapping of scientific and professional networks relevant to cardiovascular health, menopause, AI in healthcare, and gender-sensitive research has been initiated as part of the project's broader dissemination and engagement efforts. This activity aims to lay the groundwork for strategic collaborations and knowledge exchange, supporting both the dissemination of results and their long-term sustainability.

A diverse set of networks has been identified across scientific, clinical, and technological domains. These include prominent European and international associations such as the European Society of Cardiology (ESC), the International Menopause Society (IMS), and the International Society of Gynaecological Endocrinology (ISGE) and European Association of Preventive Cardiology (EAPC), among others. Several project partners maintain active roles within these networks, enabling privileged access to thematic communities and creating opportunities for synergy.

The full list of identified networks is provided in Appendix II. This list will be periodically updated and monitored over the course of the project to ensure its alignment with emerging opportunities and evolving priorities within the European and global health innovation ecosystems.

3.10.3 Stakeholder community

CAMEL is progressively building a stakeholder community composed of institutions and organisations, public and private, with whom project partners have established collaborations through previous or ongoing initiatives. This community spans academic institutions, healthcare providers, research centres, public health bodies, patient organisations, NGOs, and industry actors across Europe and Latin America. Their involvement will contribute to

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

enhancing the project's impact and ensuring the real-world relevance and sustainability of its outcomes, particularly in relation to personalised cardiovascular prevention for women.

The comprehensive list of stakeholders is included in Appendix III, and will be continuously updated throughout the project lifecycle.

3.10.4 External and partner-led events

Participation in external events and the organisation of partner-led initiatives are integral components of CARMEL's dissemination and engagement strategy.

External third-party events, including scientific conferences, workshops and congresses, offer valuable opportunities to disseminate results, foster dialogue, and build synergies across disciplines and sectors. In parallel, events initiated by CARMEL partners in the context of other projects or institutional activities represent strategic platforms to position CARMEL in ongoing conversations around cardiovascular prevention, women's health, and AI in healthcare.

A preliminary mapping of these two categories of events has been compiled and will be continuously updated to reflect new opportunities and evolving priorities. The complete list of third-party events of interest and partner-led events is available in Appendices IV and V.

3.10.5 Events organized by the CARMEL consortium

The CARMEL consortium will actively organise a series of events to support its dissemination and engagement strategy, ensuring broad visibility and stakeholder involvement across the project lifecycle. These events are strategically designed to maximize outreach, facilitate recruitment for clinical studies, disseminate research outcomes, and foster interdisciplinary dialogue.

Each clinical site participating in the project will conduct at least two national or regional dissemination events. These will serve dual purposes: first, to inform and engage potential participants in the clinical studies; and second, to share interim and final project findings with local communities and stakeholders. Whenever feasible, these events will be embedded within broader conferences or public gatherings to enhance cost-effectiveness and audience reach. The target for these activities is a minimum of 12 events with an aggregate attendance of over 200 individuals.

In addition, a final conference will be coordinated jointly by VICOM and SIT, to be held either in Spain or Brussels. This event will aim to consolidate and disseminate the project's achievements, promote dialogue with key stakeholders, and outline pathways for post-project sustainability. It is expected to attract at least 75 participants.

3.11 CARMEL External Advisory Board

To ensure high-level external guidance and quality assurance, the CARMEL consortium has established an External Advisory Board (EAB) composed of renowned experts in the fields of cardiovascular disease, Artificial Intelligence, ethics, and data protection. The EAB is designed to provide independent advice on the scientific, technical, and ethical dimensions of the project and will contribute to the strategic alignment of CARMEL's activities with broader health, research, and policy developments.

The board comprises five members, selected for their cross-sectoral expertise and geographic diversity. Their role includes reviewing project progress, providing strategic recommendations, and validating project outcomes with a critical, external perspective.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

The first formal meeting (Kick-off meeting, KoM) of the EAB is scheduled to take place at the end of Month 6 marking the beginning of its advisory engagement. The EAB's contributions will be documented and integrated into project reporting to ensure transparency and accountability throughout the project's lifecycle. Once of the potential fields of expertise and support requested to the EAB members will be their agency in order to further disseminate the project results in relevant conferences and events, such as the annual ESC Congress, where they might have contacts or be a member of the governing bodies.

3.12 Women engagement strategies

As part of Task 14.3, a comprehensive engagement strategy was co-developed by TCD and SIT to support the implementation of T4.1 Analysis of women's lived experience of menopause, specifically targeting the involvement of over 6,000 women across the six clinical sites and TCD.

At M2, TCD and SIT prepared and disseminated an **engagement guidance document** for all clinical sites and TCD, outlining a unified approach to identifying, mobilising, and engaging women participants for the initial mixed-methods study phase. This included an outreach matrix template designed to help partners map relevant stakeholders (e.g., local health networks, HCP, women's organisations, advocacy groups etc.) and systematically track outreach activities and stakeholder responses.

To support visibility and facilitate participation, a **dedicated communication plan** was launched in M4. SIT and TCD developed a press release in English that each clinical site could adapt and translate to reflect its local context. In parallel, a ready-to-use social media package was provided, including a series of three posts tailored to different engagement phases (awareness, motivation, and final call-to-action) each accompanied by branded visuals aligned with the project's visual identity.

As the campaign evolved, an informative brochure about the survey was also created in multiple languages. These tools collectively helped clinical partners to consistently and effectively disseminate the call for participation, reaching a diverse and representative cohort of women aged 40–60, including those with intellectual disabilities. More detailed information on the engagement strategies and the activities planned and carried out will be presented in Deliverable D14.3 Impact Report I.

4. Monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities

4.1 Communication and dissemination KPIs

This sub-chapter consolidates the dissemination and communication actions planned by the CAMEL consortium, linking each channel and tool, detailed in Chapter 3, to measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These indicators reflect the Strategic Objectives outlined in the project's communication and dissemination plan and will guide continuous performance monitoring and impact assessment.

The following table detailed all the planned actions along with their KPIs to be achieved over the course of the project.

Category	Action	KPIs
Branded Materials	Development of visual identity	Project Visual Identity Handbook: 1
	Communication material kit (brochure, poster, roll-up, ppt)	Kit: >1 brochure, >1 poster, >1 roll-up
Digital Channels	Project website	Visits by end of project: 5,000
	News	News published on the project website >50
	Project briefs	Projects briefs reported in the project website >8
	CVD prevention portal	Visits by end of project >10,000
	Social media activities	Avg. social media posts/week >1; Followers >2,000
	Digital newsletters	Nº of newsletters: 8
	Press brief and press releases	Press brief: 1; Project briefs delivered to mass media >10 Press releases: 6
Video	Project introduction and results videos	Nº of videos: 6; YouTube views: >3,000
Publications	Scientific articles	Nº of scientific publications: 20
Events	Participation in external events	Nº of events with CAMEL partner participation: 20
	Organisation of dissemination events by clinical sites	Nº of events: >12; Nº of attendants: 200
	Organisation of final project conference	Nº of conferences: 1; Nº of attendants: 75
	Participation in external events	Nº of events with CAMEL participation: 20
Policy Engagement	Policy briefs and stakeholder outreach	Nº of policy briefs: 1; Nº of stakeholders outreach: ≥15
Clustering & Synergies	Memoranda of understanding with projects and initiatives	Nº of MoUs: 20

Figure 12 CAMEL communication actions and KPIs

These KPIs will be monitored each 6 months in the framework of CAMEL Dashboard of KPIs, designed and deployed by Project Coordinator and addressing all the Work packages of the project.

4.2 Communication and dissemination monitoring

The monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities in CAMEL are integral to ensuring the coherence, quality, and strategic alignment of all actions with the project's objectives. This Chapter outlines the methods and procedures used to track, reflect upon, and optimise the implementation of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan across the project lifecycle.

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

In line with the best practices adopted in Horizon Europe projects, the monitoring framework for CAMEL focuses not only on tracking quantitative outputs but also on fostering internal coordination, quality assurance, and adaptive learning among project partners.

The following procedure will be implemented

- **CDE Action Plan:** a comprehensive internal CDE Action Plan will be developed and regularly updated throughout the project. This plan will map planned dissemination actions against key project outputs, internal milestones, and participation in external or partner-led events. It will serve as a reference tool to ensure consistency and proactive planning of all CDE activities.
- **Networking and clustering database updates:** as described in Section 3.10, a dedicated Database for networking and clustering activities has been created to monitor cross-project engagement and partnership building efforts. This database will be continuously updated by all partners and reviewed.
- **Notification of upcoming CD opportunities:** all partners are required to inform the WP14-15-16 leader (SIT) and the Project Coordinator (VICOM) whenever new dissemination or engagement opportunities arise. SIT will support the implementation of these activities where needed, providing assistance with content creation, branding, translation, and stakeholder targeting.
- **Reporting of activities:** since the beginning of the project, each partner has been asked to report monthly on their communication and dissemination activities using a shared monitoring database. This partner-level reporting tool, structured as a collaborative Excel file, captures key information such as the type of activity, date, audience, estimated reach, and proof of dissemination (e.g. links or screenshots). The system ensures transparency and visibility of all consortium-level outreach actions, maximises synergies, and supports timely reporting to the European Commission. The reporting of CDE activities to the EC will be coordinated by SIT both in the technical Periodic Report as well as in SYGMA.
- **Review of activities:** to ensure that the dissemination and communication strategy remains responsive and effective, internal review sessions will be held twice per year, in the framework of project meetings. During these sessions, SIT will present an overview of dissemination progress, including:
 - Performance insights from social media, newsletters, and website analytics;
 - Summary of partner activities collected through the reporting database;
 - Highlights of major events.If needed, additional review sessions may be scheduled outside the regular project meetings to address urgent or strategic adjustments.
- **Content quality assurance:** as already outlined in Section 2.9, all communication materials with high visibility or sensitive content (e.g., press releases, videos, campaign visuals, materials targeting clinical study participants) are subject to an internal **validation process**. This process includes review by the WP14 leader and, where relevant, by partners with domain-specific expertise or involvement in the concerned activities (e.g., clinical sites or WP4 leader). This approach ensures that all public-facing outputs are:
 - Factually accurate and aligned with CAMEL's scientific and ethical standards;
 - Inclusive, accessible, and gender-sensitive;
 - Compliant with Horizon Europe visibility and communication guidelines.

Monitoring insights will also feed into the continuous assessment of KPIs outlined in Section 4.1, supporting a data-informed refinement of the CDE strategy over time.

5. Guide on dissemination and communication activities

This Section provides a practical guide for all consortium partners contributing to the dissemination and communication activities of the CAMEL project. It summarises the guiding principles, recommended procedures, and good practices to ensure that all content is coherent, impactful, and aligned with the project's identity and objectives.

Key principles

All dissemination and communication activities should be developed in line with the following principles:

- **Clarity:** use accessible and jargon-free language whenever possible;
- **Inclusiveness:** ensure gender-sensitive, culturally appropriate, and audience-specific language;
- **Consistency:** follow the project's official visual identity, logos, templates, and tone;
- **Visibility:** always include the CAMEL and EU logo;
- **Alignment:** ensure that the content reflects the project's values, milestones, and messages;
- **Accessibility:** include alternative text in images, graphs and diagrams, avoid stereotyping or labelling language on age, gender, disability and social-economic groups.

Internal review and coordination

Dissemination content produced by partners does **not require mandatory validation** by the WP14 leader (SIT), but it is **strongly recommended** that partners share drafts with SIT for a rapid review. This helps ensure consistency, proper use of templates and disclaimers, and alignment with Horizon Europe communication standards.

SIT is available to provide:

- Language and accessibility checks;
- Visual identity and formatting support;
- Strategic advice for adapting content to specific target groups;

Channels and tools

Partners are encouraged to disseminate CAMEL-related messages through their own institutional and professional channels, such as:

- Institutional websites and blogs;
- Email newsletters or mailing lists;
- Social media accounts (LinkedIn, X, Facebook, etc.);
- Public-facing events, lectures, or presentations;
- Internal or sectoral publications, reports;

In all cases, content should refer back to the project website and/or official communication channels, to maintain consistency and central visibility.

Good practices for visibility

To ensure effective communication and alignment with EU visibility rules, partners should:

- Use the official CAMEL templates and visual identity elements;
- Display the EU emblem and the sentence: "*Funded by the European Union*";
- Include the disclaimer: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101156210. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible.";

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

- Tailor the tone and format to the intended audience (scientific, public, policymaker, etc.);
- Where possible, enrich content with visual or multimedia elements (e.g., infographics, photos, short videos);

Contact and support

SIT remains available throughout the project to provide support, feedback, and strategic input on dissemination content. Partners are encouraged to reach out via email if they wish to receive feedback on drafts, advice on audience targeting, or support in adapting materials for specific channels.

6. Exploitation strategy

This Section outlines the overarching objectives and framework of the exploitation strategy within the CAMEL project. Exploitation activities aim to ensure that the project's most valuable scientific, technological, and societal outputs, referred to as Key Exploitable Results (KERs), are effectively transformed into sustainable solutions that deliver long-term impact beyond the project's duration.

The exploitation strategy serves multiple purposes:

- To maximise the uptake of CAMEL's AI-driven risk stratification models, digital ecosystem, and engagement tools across healthcare systems, policy frameworks, and innovation markets.
- To facilitate the access to the outcomes of the CAMEL co-creation sessions and clinical studies, so that they are actionable by healthcare professionals, policy makers, women, and other key stakeholders.
- To assist the CAMEL partners with the preparation of the ground for the potential commercialisation or institutional adoption of project outputs, aligning with the regulatory, ethical, and societal context of personalised prevention in women's cardiovascular health.
- To support the long-term sustainability of CAMEL results through alignment with EU health strategies, integration pathways in national systems, and collaboration with industry and public health actors.

Overall, the CAMEL's exploitation strategy will leverage the experience and competences promoted through the integrated communication effort of all CAMEL partners, as the project prepares for the Communication for Exploitation and Sustainability final phase, which prevails in the last twenty months of the project's execution, when CAMEL results, products and solutions are available and the ultimate effort for broadcast and targeted communication is carried out by all CAMEL partners to ensure the successful exploitation and sustainability of the project's results.

CAMEL's exploitation planning process starts with the initial definition of the planned portfolio of CAMEL KERs, whose preliminary scope will be further developed, refined, and iteratively improved in the course of the exploitation process. The CAMEL offer's scope is thus the reference for a dedicated market analysis, as well as for the business and marketing plan, highlighting CAMEL's competitive advantage and market positioning. The market analysis comprises a PESTEL (political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal and ethical) analysis, a sound competitors' assessment with benchmarking contours and the performance of market segmentation. The evaluation of the competition intensity in the market is instrumental to determine the level of desirability for the new CAMEL offer for the respective market segment, allowing to identify CAMEL's unique selling proposition and competitive advantage, to determine the best market positioning for each targeted market.

The exploitation strategy also provides a reference for consortium partners to define their own exploitation interests, explore synergies, and co-develop models for value creation, whether through policy, clinical practice, education, or business opportunities.

6.1 Key exploitable results

Based on the GA, CAMEL is expected to generate a set of ten KERs, each representing a concrete output of scientific, clinical, technological, or strategic value. These results are designed to create societal, policy, and market impact by addressing the urgent need for personalised and gender-sensitive cardiovascular (CVD) prevention strategies. The following table outlines the preliminary list of KERs, including their description, targeted stakeholders, and initial exploitation pathways, as foreseen in the GA:

Key Exploitation Results	Del.	Target Groups	Preliminary exploitation pathways
KER1 CVD-RA AI models for women 40- 60y from multiple data sources	D7.1	HCPS, Policy, health auth, research, academia	Scientific publications, clinical validation & adoption, further R&I, licensing, AI marketplace, spin-off
KER2 CAMEL Stratification Scheme for CVD Personalised Prevention (Figure 3)	D8.1	HCPS, Policy, health auth, research, academia	Clinical validation in further R&I projects, healthcare integration
KER3 Self-management ecosystem for CVD prevention (apps, coach, wearables).	D13.5 D10.1 D10.2	HCPS, Policy, health authorities	Clinical validation in further R&I projects, licensing, market access
KER4 Policy Brief and Clinical pathways and guidelines for CVD Prevention and Screening programmes	D16.2	HCPS, Policy, health authorities	Scientific publications and meetings, policy advocacy, clinical guidelines
KER5 CAMEL Women's CVD Prevention Portal and asApp	D14.2	Policy, health auth, Patients & general public	Sustainability by endorsement of public health authorities
KER6 Digital Platform to collect and process multiple data sources and models	D9.1	HCPS, Policy, health authorities, industry	Further R&I, adaptation to other sectors. Licensing schemes.
KER7 Biobank with 175.000 aliquots from 8,000 samples for CVD research in women	D13.7	Research, academia	Open access to Biobank resources by the overall R&I community
KER8 New CVD screening and monitoring tech (lipoproteins, skin patch, iBreve)	D13.5	HCPS, Policy, health authorities, industry	Further R&I, clinical validation, certification, licensing, spin-off
KER9 Regulatory Roadmap for certification of the CVD-RA models and ecosystem of apps and devices.	D13.5	CAMEL tech partners	Clinical validation in further R&I projects, MDR certification for software as medical device (SaMD)
KER10 Business models and exploitation plans for transfer of results.	D16.1	CAMEL tech partners	Licensing schemes with healthcare providers

Table 4 CAMEL Preliminary Key Exploitable Results

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

As part of the Innovation Management carried out by the Coordinator, VICOM in the framework of WP1-2-3, every 20 months, the KER maturity will be analysed by the KER owners with VICOM in the framework of tasks T1.2, T2.2., and T3.2 devoted to the scientific, technical and innovation management.

This assessment will involve evaluating the KERs from three key perspectives, relevant for the accessibility and re-usability of the research outputs:

- **Technology Readiness Level (TRL):** A review of the technological advancements and readiness of each KER, including any progress made towards innovation and development goals.
- **Market Readiness Level (MRL):** An evaluation of the market potential of each KER, focusing on aspects such as market demand, competition, and potential for commercialization or application.
- **Social Readiness Level (SRL):** An analysis of the societal impact and readiness of each KER, considering factors such as societal acceptance, regulatory requirements, and ethical implications.

In this assessment, VICOM might rely in accessible innovative solutions, such as the [MultiRATE](#) project's Holistic Readiness Level calculator to measure the holistic maturity of a product/system/process developed in R&I projects, which considers even a broader number of Readiness levels, including Legal, Privacy and Ethics readiness, Security readiness and Manufacturing readiness levels. Results from the characterisation of KER will be reported in the Management Reports.

6.2 Market analysis

As part of the exploitation strategy, PARTICLE will coordinate a market analysis to take place in WP15, involving i) a general overview of the market; ii) a characterisation of the CAMEL KERs; iii) a competitive positioning analysis, considering SWOT and PESTEL tools, Key Success Factors (KSF) and prevailing market opportunities and barriers.

The competitive advantage is an attribute that allows an organisation to outperform its competitors. In CAMEL's context, competitive advantage refers to the set of factors that allow the CAMEL approach and technologies to deliver more advanced or higher quality cardiovascular health services for women.

Amongst the different tools enabling the understanding of competitive advantage, the SWOT analysis allows CAMEL partners to assess the internal (strengths and weaknesses) and external (opportunities and threats) factors that influence a better use of resources and help the definition of a successful business strategy for the CAMEL results. The goal is to emphasise CAMEL's strengths and mitigate its weaknesses (so as not to be explored by competitors), while being aware of existing threats and leveraging on actionable opportunities. In addition, the PESTEL Framework provides a strategic macro-level analysis of a set of factors of a Political, Economic, Social, Technological (and Technical), Environmental and Legal (Ethical and Standardisation) nature influencing the market for the CAMEL results, in order to better understand if the external context involving CAMEL is fitted to accommodate CAMEL's ambitious objective of establishing a unique positioning in the European cardiovascular prevention health community. Further, the identification of the KSF to foster the adoption of the CAMEL vision and technologies is fundamental as part of the exploitation strategy, especially when CAMEL's offer is beyond the current state-of-the-art and its early adoption may entail risks that cause constraints to the exploitable results' market penetration and uptake, including as a routine part of clinical practice. Finally, the preparation of the CAMEL market deployment requires a discussion among the CAMEL partners about the challenges and opportunities involving the market introduction of CAMEL in future years. Relevant business impact drivers will help to complete the CAMEL market

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

analysis and provide a sustained foundation for the CAMEL exploitation activities embraced individually or jointly by the CAMEL partners.

Overall, the market analysis contributes to the success of the CAMEL's exploitation strategy by helping to identify potential applications and commercialisation opportunities for project results, enabling CAMEL partners to tailor their strategies and develop effective business models. Understanding the market landscape, competition, industry trends and competitive advantages allows for a more targeted and efficient approach to maximising the commercial potential of innovations.

The CAMEL market analysis and strategy will be reported in Deliverable D15.1 by M36.

6.3 Intellectual property rights audit

As part of the exploitation strategy's market analysis, Project Coordinator, VICOM, will carry out an Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) audit that considers the CAMEL partners' background and foreground (results) knowledge, individually or jointly developed, in order to respect the IPR imperatives and any applicable non-disclosure agreements.

Given that exploitation often hinges on the ownership and sharing of innovative assets, setting up an IPR foundation is vital for safeguarding these innovations and promoting collaborative benefit. Defining the background IPR (pre-existing knowledge, technologies, or methodologies that each partner brings into the CAMEL project) ensures clarity on what is owned by whom from the start, enabling smoother collaboration and preventing potential conflicts. By delineating these assets, the groundwork is laid for fair and effective exploitation of results that build upon existing knowledge. The IPR for newly developed technologies, knowledge, or processes generated within the CAMEL project is equally crucial. The ownership, access rights, and utilization policies for these foreground innovations, ensuring that each partner has a defined pathway to exploit their contributions. Establishing these policies early on provides clarity for future applications, licensing opportunities, and collaborative use within and beyond the project's scope.

Based on the IPR audit, it is possible to create an IPR framework to provide each CAMEL partner with a clear understanding of their rights, obligations, and opportunities related to intellectual property, fostering an environment conducive to open collaboration and sustainable innovation.

VICOM will conduct three IPR audits every 20 months, in alignment with the project's reporting periods (M20, M40, M60). The IPR audit template is available on D1.1 Project Management Handbook.

These audits will help identify important aspects of the results produced by CAMEL, such as:

- Control of access rights necessary for project implementation.
- Control of third-party software and commercial hardware used in the project.
- Control of third-party intellectual property rights utilized during implementation.
- Background IP from each partner used in the project.
- Foreground IP generated during the project.

Also, these audits may serve as a basis for agreeing on Joint Ownership Agreements (JOAs), if there are joint results, as well as future exploitation pathways and licenses beyond the project, ensuring that the project remains compliant with the conditions laid out in the Consortium Agreement and maintain transparency throughout its lifecycle. Proper IPR management is essential to transforming CAMEL's results into successful market innovations.

6.4 CAMEL Business Plan

Based upon the findings of the market analysis, and with the contributions from all CAMEL partners, PARTICLE will coordinate the creation of the CAMEL Business Plan as the blueprint for viable business models and the CAMEL partners' individual and joint exploitation activities, aim to maximise the return on investment of the research and innovation activities developed, to deliver cost-effective benefits for end-users, and to leverage business and commercial impact.

Based upon the findings of the market analysis, PARTICLE will coordinate with the contributions from all CAMEL partners to establish the CAMEL Business Plan as the blueprint for viable business models and the CAMEL partners' individual and joint exploitation activities, aiming to maximise the return on investment of the research and innovation activities developed, to deliver cost-effective benefits for end-users, and to leverage business and commercial impact.

To introduce the novel CAMEL approach to cardiovascular prevention health programmes for women in the European market requires considerable investments that address patient safety concerns, the adaptation of clinical practice and the adoption of novel digital technologies, including AI-powered cardiovascular risk assessment and stratification models. In order to decide on investments, investors (payable customers or decision-makers) expect a sound, feasible and robust business plan that presents viable business models, often developed on the basis of a framework that addresses the technology, the organisation, the services and the financial aspects. Osterwalder's business canvas and value network diagrams support the illustration and understanding of the business cases' strengths and weaknesses to better establish the business potential of the CAMEL results, focused on the creation of value for the customer. The generation of value is further enabled by the delineation of a marketing strategy that accounts for four major impact axes, technology, knowledge, business and society, and allows to increase the business-related opportunities that support the CAMEL exploitation activities.

Considering a five-year timeframe following the project's conclusion, the CAMEL Business Plan will consider that the consortium partners are of different topology: (a) industrial partners; (b) academic partners; and (c) end-users. Depending on the nature of the exploitable result and the partner's typology, a strategy will be formulated to pursue the in-breadth development, as well as the in-depth evolution, of the CAMEL results, securing their continuation and uptake in the market, through two alternative sustainability and exploitation strategies: scientific exploitation and commercial exploitation. With the identification of the CAMEL KERS, the assessment of the market's characteristics and the establishment of the CAMEL's business potential, based on competitive advantage and viable market positioning, CAMEL partners are able to define the CAMEL business models for collective exploitation, identify individual exploitation plans and establish the roadmap for the broad adoption and uptake of the CAMEL results across Europe and beyond.

The CAMEL Business Models and Exploitation Plan will be reported in M60.

7. Conclusions

This CDE Plan sets out a comprehensive, stakeholder-driven roadmap for promoting the CAMEL project throughout its five-year duration and ensuring its impact beyond the research context. It defines tailored messages, tools, and actions that reflect the project's commitment to gender-sensitive innovation in cardiovascular prevention for women aged 40–60.

Throughout the project's lifetime, this plan will guide all partners in effectively reaching key audiences, supporting the adoption of CAMEL's tools, and building strategic alliances for clinical uptake, market scalability, and integration into European policy frameworks. The CDE

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

strategy will remain adaptive, evolving in response to project milestones, stakeholder engagement, and emerging opportunities throughout the project duration.

As the project advances, further iterations of this plan will assess implementation progress, refine approaches, and deepen impact pathways, ensuring the long-term sustainability and relevance of CARMEL's innovations.

Appendices

Appendix I – Related projects

No	Project Acronym	Project Name (full name, if applicable)	Funding Program
1	CVD-Link	A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions	HE
2	LUCIA	Understanding Lung Cancer Related Risk Factor and their Impact	HE
3	SYNTHEMA	Synthetic haematological data over federated computing frameworks	HE
4	CoroPrevention	Personalized Prevention for Coronary Heart Disease	H2020
5	AI4HF	Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence for Personalised Risk Assessment in Chronic Heart Failure (AI4HF)	HEU
6	DataTools4Heart	A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy	HEU
7	CARDIOCARE	An Interdisciplinary Approach for the Management of the Elderly Multimorbid Patient with Breast Cancer Therapy Induced Cardiac Toxicity	H2020
8	EHRA-PATHS	Addressing multimorbidity in elderly atrial fibrillation patients through interdisciplinary, patient-centred, systematic care pathways	H2020
9	AtheroNET	Network for implementing multiomic approaches in atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease prevention and research	COST ACTION
10	TIMELY	A patient-centered early risk prediction, prevention, and intervention platform to support the continuum of care in coronary artery disease (CAD) using eHealth and artificial intelligence	H2020
11	CORDELIA	Collaborative cOHORTS Reassembled Data to study mechanisms and Longterm Incidence of chronic diseases	NextGenEU
12	PERSUADE	na	ERA4Health CARDINNOV
13	OPADE	Optimise and predict antidepressant efficacy for patient with major depressive disorders using multi-omics analysis and AI-predictive tool	HE
14	MultiPRESS	Multiscale Imaging of Cardiovascular Pressure Gradients – a Paradigm Shift in Hemodynamic Risk Prediction	HE
15	AI4HF	Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence for Personalised Risk Assessment in Chronic Heart Failure	HE
16	MicroMechAtheros	Identifying Atherosclerotic Plaques at Risk: A Microstructure-based Biomechanistic Approach	HE
17	iCARE4CVD	INDIVIDUALISED CARE FROM EARLY RISK OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE TO ESTABLISHED HEART FAILURE	HE
18	FH-EARLY	NEW STRATEGIES FOR THE EARLY DIAGNOSIS, RISK STRATIFICATION AND CO-MANAGEMENT OF FAMILIAL HYPERCHOLESTEROLEMIA	HE
19	SMHEART	Smart Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Delivering One-Click and Comprehensive Assessment of Cardiovascular Diseases	HE

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

No	Project Acronym	Project Name (full name, if applicable)	Funding Program
20	INSIDE-HEART	multi-disciplinary, multi-Sectoral and multi-national training network on Digital biomarkers for supraventricular arrhythmia characterization and Risk assessment	HE
21	VASCUL-AID	DEVELOPING TRUSTWORTHY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)-DRIVEN TOOLS TO PREDICT VASCULAR DISEASE RISK AND PROGRESSION	HE
22	BISCUITS	Multi-Omics-based Biomarker Signatures of dietary Carbohydrates Quality and risk of chronic diseases.	HE
23	STIMULUS	Speckle Technology and Digital Biomarkers of Microvascular Function for Monitoring Cardiovascular Diseases	HE
24	STIMULUS	Speckle Technology and Digital Biomarkers of Microvascular Function for Monitoring Cardiovascular Diseases	HE
25	TRUSTroke	TRUSTWORTHY AI FOR IMPROVEMENT OF STROKE OUTCOMES	HE
26	FragMent	Geographic environments, daily activities and stress: a study on the space-time fragmentation of exposure patterns	HE
27	ARTEMIS	Accelerating the Translation of virtual twins towards a personalised Management of fatty liver patients	HE
28	HyperK	Differential effects of dietary potassium intake on blood pressure	HE
29	TRIGGER	Solutions for mitigating climate-induced health threats	HE
30	PREPARE	Precision medicine to Prevent Arrhythmic Events in athletes	HE
31	SMARTSHAPE	Development of a smart shape-memory sensor for biological pressure monitoring applications	HE
32	Neuroheart	The cardiac neurovascular interface in aging	HE
33	ELVIS	ELEM Virtual Heart Populations for Supercomputers	HE
34	SUNRISE	Sustainable interventions and healthy behaviors for adolescent primary prevention of cancer with digital tools	HE
35	AI4Health	Artificial Intelligence for Smart Healthcare and Medicine	NextGenEU
36	IDHERA	Integration of Heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance	IHI
37	VOLABIOS	Validation and Comparative Multi-Omics Benchmarking of Fluid-Derived Volatilomics Biomarkers for the Prevention and Early detection of Schizophrenia	HE
38	MHS	The Maternal Health Study	Australian funders
39	SGLT2-HYPE	SGLT2 INHIBITION FOR CARDIOVASCULAR ENDPOINT REDUCTION IN HYPERTENSION (SGLT2-HYPE)	HE
40	CODIET	Combatting diet related non-communicable disease through enhanced surveillance.	HE
41	CORIMAGEN	Comprehensive protocol for the stratification, diagnosis, and prevention of coronary heart disease in women aged 45 to 65	Valencian Innovation Agency
42	ADAIR	Advances in Diagnosis and Prognosis of Atherosclerosis for High-Risk Diabetic Patients	Ministry of Science and Innovation Government of Spain

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

No	Project Acronym	Project Name (full name, if applicable)	Funding Program
43	ARTIACAR	Análisis de Retina con Tecnologías de Inteligencia Artificial para la Predicción y Evaluación de Enfermedades Cardiovasculares	Convocatoria de Proyectos de I+D+i en Colaboración, Público-Privada 2022
44	SMENS	Menstrual health, mental health and quality of life in Spain: mixed-methods and participatory study to co-create an evidence-based guideline	ISCIII
46	GWAS	THE FIRST GENOME-WIDE ASSOCIATION STUDY (GWAS) WITH 10-YEAR POPULATION-BASED CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN MORE THAN 100,000 PARTICIPANTS TO PERSONALISE CARDIOVASCULAR PREVENTION IN SPAIN	ISCIII
47	ONCOSCREEN	A European “shield” against colorectal cancer based on novel, more precise and affordable risk-based screening methods and viable policy pathways	HE
48	REBECCA	REsearch on BrEast Cancer induced chronic conditions supported by Causal Analysis of multi-source data/REBECCA	H2020
49	AI4LUNGS	AI-BASED PERSONALISED CARE FOR RESPIRATORY DISEASE USING MULTI-MODAL DATA IN PATIENT STRATIFICATION	HE

Appendix II – Established networks

No	Network Name	Category (e.g., Scientific, Clinical, Technological)	Country/Region
1	CNIC	Scientific	Spain
2	CIBER CV	Scientific	Spain
3	Red Española de Modelización Computacional Cardiaca	Scientific	Spain
4	European Menopause and Andropause Society - EMAS	Scientific	Europe
5	North America Menopause Society - NAMS	Scientific	Northern America
6	International Menopause Society - IMS	Scientific	Global
7	International Society of Gynecological Endocrinology - ISGE	Scientific	Global
8	European Society of Endocrinology - ESE	Scientific	Europe
9	OHDSI Spain	Scientific	Spain
10	EHDEN	Scientific	International
11	Sociedades de cardiología andaluzas	Scientific	Spain
12	Sociedades de cardiología nacionales	Scientific	Spain
13	Sociedades de ginecología	Scientific	Spain
14	Sociedad de Medicina de Familia y Comunitaria (semFYC)	Scientific	Spain
15	Sociedad Española de Directivos de Atención Primaria (SEDAP)	Scientific	Spain
16	Sociedad Española de Médicos de Atención Primaria (SEMERGEN)	Scientific	Spain
17	Fundación redGDPS	Scientific	Spain
18	ESC - European Society of Cardiology	scientific	Europe
19	European Association of Preventive Cardiology	Scientific	Global
20	Red de Investigación en Cronicidad, Atención Primaria y Prevención y Promoción de la Salud (RICAPPS). Research Network on Chronic Disease, Primary Care and Prevention and Health Promotion.	Scientific, Clinical	Basque Country (ES)
21	Big Data Value Association (BDVA)	Scientific, Technological	Europe
22	European Technology Platform for communications networks and services (NetWorld2020)	Scientific, Technological	Europe

Appendix III - Known stakeholders

No	Organization Name	Category (university, research center, SME)	Country
1	WoW (Women of Wearables)	Association	Global
2	St James's Hospital	Clinical	Ireland
3	Tallaght University Hospital	Clinical	Ireland
4	Fundación Keralty	Foundation	Colombia
5	Servicio Andaluz de Salud (SAS)	Healthcare provider	Spain
6	Colsanitas	Healthcare providers - specialized care - primary care	Colombia
7	Organización de Asociaciones de Pacientes. Fundación Española del Corazón	National Foundation	Spain
8	Mujeres para la Salud	National organization	Spain
9	Plataforma de Organizaciones de Pacientes (POP)	National organization	Spain
10	European Society of Cardiology	NGO	France
11	Fundación Intrás	NGO	Spain
12	PROLEPSIS Civil Law Non-Profit Organization of Preventive Environmental and Occupational Medicine	NGO	Greece
13	WHO	Organization	Worldwide
14	Azienda Provinciale per i Servizi Sanitari	public body	Italy
15	Osakidetza	Public health service	Spain
16	ALMIRALL SA	R&D - therapeutical areas	-
17	FISABIO	Research Center	Spain
18	INCLIVA	Research Center	Spain
19	Sociedad Colombiana de Cardiología y cirugía cardiovascular	Scientific	Colombia
20	LEITAT	SME	Spain
21	GE Medical Systems	Technology provider	Europe
22	UNISANITAS	University	Colombia
23	University College Cork	University	Ireland
24	Atlantic Technological University of Ireland	University	Ireland
25	Royal College of Surgeons	University	Ireland
26	Universitat Pompeu Fabra	University	Spain
27	Universitat Politècnica de Valencia	University	Spain
28	Maastricht University	University	Netherlands
29	MLU University	University	Germany
30	University of Valencia-Polibienestar	University	Spain
31	University of Lubjana	University	Slovenia
32	Rotterdam University	University	Netherlands
33	Universitat de Barcelona	University	Spain
34	Universität Heidelberg	University	Germany
35	ASTANGU KUTSEREHABILITATSIOONI KESKUS	University	Estonia
36	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	University	Greece
37	Laurea University of Applied Sciences	University	Finland
38	Thomas More Kempen	University	Belgium

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

No	Organization Name	Category (university, research center, SME)	Country
39	Center for Research and Technology Hellas Certh	University	Greece
40	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GMBH	University	Austria
41	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid	University	Spain

Appendix IV – Relevant future events

No	Event Name	Category (e.g., conference, workshop, seminar, panel discussion etc.)	Date	Location	Organizers	Website or link of the event
1	EMAS 15th European Congress	Conference	May-25	Valencia, Spain	EMAS	https://emas-online.org/congresses-courses/
2	SAC 2025	Regional congress	May-25	Jaén, Spain	Andalusian Cardiology Society	https://www.congresosacardiologia.com/
3	3rd Andalusian redGDPS Conference	Regional congress (Andalusia)	May-25	Sevilla, Spain	Fundación redGDPS	https://www.redgdps.org/iii-jornadas-redgdps-anadaluca-20250325/
4	Jornadas de la Red Española de Modelización Computacional Cardíaca	Workshop	Jun-25	Valencia, Spain	VHEART	https://redmodcard.webs.upv.es/?tribe_events=jornadas-de-la-red-espanola-de-modelizacion-computacional-cardiaca
5	International Conference of AI in Medicine	Conference	Jun-25	Pavia, Italy	Research community	https://aime25.aimedicine.info/
6	HLTH Europe	Mixed	Jun-25	Amsterdam, Netherlands	HLTH Inc.	https://europe.hlth.com/
7	ESC Congress25	European congress	Aug-25	Madrid, Spain	European Cardiology Society	https://www.escardio.org/Congresses-Events/ESC-Congress
8	International Conference on Computational Intelligence Methods for Bioinformatics and Biostatistics	Conference	Sep-25	Milan, Italy	European Neural Network Society / IEEE Computational Intelligence Society	https://www.bioinformatics.polimi.it/CIBB2025/
9	NAMS Annual meeting	Conference	Oct-25	Florida, USA	NAMS	https://menopause.org/annual-meetings/2025-annual-meeting
10	46th Panhellenic Cardiology Congress	Conference	Oct-25	Athens, Greece	Hellenic Society of Cardiology	

D14.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

No	Event Name	Category (e.g., conference, workshop, seminar, panel discussion etc.)	Date	Location	Organizers	Website or link of the event
11	6th Panhellenic Scientific Conference of Obstetrics and Gynecology	Conference	Oct-25	Athens, Greece	Hellenic Society of OBGYN	
12	SEC CONGRESS 2025	National congress	Oct-25	Granada, Spain	Spanish Cardiology Society	https://web.congresosec.org/
13	47th SEMERGEN Congress	National congress	Oct-25	Granada, Spain	Primary Care Physician Spanish Society	https://semergen.es/congresonacional/?seccion=informacion&subSeccion=salutacion
14	Big Data & AI World	Showcase	Oct-25	Madrid, Spain	CloserStill Media	https://www.bigdataworld.es/
15	ESC Digital and AI summit	Conference	Nov-25	Berlin, Germany	ESC	https://www.escardio.org/Congresses-Events/ESC-Digital-AI-Summit
16	XLV semFYC	National congress	Nov-25	Madrid, Spain	Family Physician Spanish Society	https://congresodelasemfyc.com/
17	European Big Data Value Forum	Mixed	Nov-25	Denmark	BDVA	https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/
18	Big Data Conference Europe	Conference	Nov-25	Vilnius, Lithuania	UAB DATA MINER	https://bigdataconference.eu/
19	XLV SEMFYC Congress (Spanish Society of Family and Community Medicine)	Conference	Nov-25	Madrid, Spain	SsemFYC	https://congresodelasemfyc.com/
20	Gynecological Endocrinology the 40 Anniversary Congress	Conference	Mar-26	Rome, Italy	ISGE	https://isge2026.isgesociety.com/
21	AI Health world Summit	Conference	2026	Not available yet	Singhealth DUKE NUS Academic Medical Center	https://healthsummit.ai/
22	World Digital Healthcare and AI Summit	Conference	2027	Not available yet	Luxatia International	https://www.luxatiainternational.com/product/world-digital-healthcare-and-ai-summit

Appendix V – Events organized by partners

N.	Partner organizing	Event Name	Category (e.g., conference, workshop, seminar, panel discussion etc.)	Date	Location/Mode
1	BK	Plenary sessions for the managers of the units of Primary Care	Panel discussion	Mar-25	OSI Donostialdea (San Sebastian - Donostia, Spain)
2	SNSI	Hamsa - Israel-EU Annual Horizon Europe Award Ceremony	Award ceremony	Mar-25	Tel-Aviv, Israel
3	BIO	Plenary sessions for the managers of the units of Primary Care	Panel discussion	Mar-25	OSI Donostialdea (San Sebastian - Donostia, Spain)
4	SNSI	2025 MRS Spring Event	Conference	Apr-25	Seattle, WA, USA
5	SAS & FISEVI	Innodata 2025	National Congress	Sep-25	Seville, Spain
6	SNSI	VOLABIOS	Meeting of EU project	Sep-25	Haifa, Israel
7	SAS & FISEVI	Meeting of the Cardiovascular Thrombosis Working Group of the Spanish Society of Cardiology.	National Meeting	Oct-25	Seville, Spain
8	NKUA	Biannual Hellenic Menopause Congress	Conference	Dec-25	Athens
9	BK & BIO	Biogipuzkoa Seminars	Weekly Seminars at the IIS Biogipuzkoa	2025	Biogipuzkoa (San Sebastian - Donostia, Spain)
10	NKUA	11th Panhellenic congress of Gynaecological Endocrinology	Conference	Jan-26	Thessaloniki. Greece
11	ASC	Women & cardiovascular health	Conference	2026	Valencia, Spain
12	KER	Congreso salud digital - IA	Conference	2027	Bogotá, Colombia / Hybrid